

D6.1

Preliminary LCA and LCC Assessment

version 1.0

Work Package	WP6
Task	T6.1
Due date	30-09-2025
Submission date	15-10-2025
Deliverable lead	NTT
Version	v1.0
Authors	Matteo Maccanti (NTT), Elena Marotto (NTT), Daniele Spinelli (NTT)
Reviewers	Magda Spella (FORTH), Spyros Yannopoulos (FORTH), Despoina Batsouli (ADA), Athanasios Masouras (PLE)

Abstract

This Deliverable 6.1 presents a preliminary sustainability assessment of graphene-based technologies developed within the GRAPHERGIA project. Three demonstrators are analysed: (1) self-charging textiles for energy harvesting and storage, (2) self-powered aerospace sensors embedded in composites, and (3) graphene-enhanced lithium-ion battery modules for space applications. The study applies Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Eco-Cost methodologies, following ISO 14040/14044 standards and using SimaPro with Ecoinvent database. Results identify environmental and economic hotspots, highlight potential cost-reduction pathways, and provide early guidance for eco-design strategies. Despite current limitations, such as reliance on lab-scale data and exclusion of end-of-life scenarios, the work establishes a solid basis for integrating sustainability into graphene-based innovation, contributing to the European Green Deal and circular economy objectives.

Keywords

Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Costing, Eco-Cost, Graphene, Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), Triboelectric nanogenerator (TENGs), Internet of Things (IoT), Smart Textiles.

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	01-10-2025	6.1 - Draft version for internal review	Matteo Maccanti (NTT) Elena Marotto (NTT) Daniele Spinelli (NTT)
v0.2	04-10-2025	Reviewed by the partners	Magda Spella (FORTH) Spyros Yannopoulos (FORTH)
v0.3	10-10-2025	6.1 – Revised version with comments integration	Matteo Maccanti (NTT) Elena Marotto (NTT) Daniele Spinelli (NTT)
v0.4	14-10-2025	Reviewed by the partners	Magda Spella (FORTH) Despoina Batsouli (ADA) Athanasios Masouras (PLE)
v.05	15-10-2025	6.1 – Revised version with comments integration	Matteo Maccanti (NTT)
v1.0	15-10-2025	Final version	Magda Spella (FORTH) Spyros Yannopoulos (FORTH)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation, and figures available in this deliverable are provided by the GRAPHERGIA project's consortium under EC grant agreement **101120832** and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein. The contents of this deliverable are presented for informational purposes only and are subject to the pending approval of the European Commission (EC). The information, data, and conclusions presented herein may undergo revisions or modifications following the review and approval process by the European Commission. Recipients of this document are advised that any actions, decisions, or reliance on the information provided should be exercised with caution until the final approval from the European Commission is obtained. The authors and distributors of this deliverable shall not be held liable for any consequences arising from the use of information that has not yet received official European Commission approval.

Copyright notice

© GRAPHERGIA 2023-2027

This project is supported by the European Union, under Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement n.101120832)

© GRAPHERGIA 2023-2027

Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe Programme

Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to GRAPHERGIA project and Commission Services

✓

PENDING FOR EC APPROVAL

Table of contents

Executive summary	10
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Description of the document	12
1.2 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable	13
2 Methodology	15
2.1 Goal and scope	15
2.2 Methodology for Life Cycle Assessment	17
2.3 Methodology for Life Cycle Costing	18
2.4 Methodology for Eco-Cost	19
2.5 Limitations of the Study	21
2.6 Future Perspectives	23
2.7 Benchmarking Definition and Reference Systems	23
3 GRAPHERGIA technology	25
3.1 Graphene	25
3.2 Triboelectric Nanogenerators	26
3.3 Smart Textiles for Wearable Energy and Graphene Applications	27
3.4 Lithium-ion Batteries: Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Costing and Eco-Costs	30
4 GRAPHERGIA data analysis	37
4.1 Life Cycle Assessment of Demonstrator #1: data analysis for smart textiles	37
4.1.1 Preliminary LCA Results for Demonstrator #1	41
4.1.2 Preliminary Eco-Cost Results for Demonstrator#1	44
4.2 Life Cycle Assessment of Demonstrator #3: data analysis LIBs for space applications	48
4.2.1 Preliminary LCA Results for Demonstrator #3	51
4.2.2 Preliminary Eco-Cost Results for Demonstrator #3	55
5 Preliminary evaluation and conclusions	57
6 References	60
7 Appendix	68

List of figures

Figure 1 - Demonstrator #1: Self-charging textile for energy harvesting and storage.....	16
Figure 2 - Demonstrator #2: Self-powered wireless sensor embedded in aerospace composite structures	16
Figure 3 - Demonstrator #3: Graphene-based LIBs battery module for space applications	17
Figure 4 - Stages of an LCA framework (ISO 14040).....	18
Figure 5 - Percentage Categories Process (%).....	43
Figure 6 - CF for Damage Category.....	44
Figure 7 - Overall Eco-Cost for rGO treated textile	46
Figure 8 - PLE process production of LIB pouch cell	48
Figure 9 - CF Damage Category.....	54
Figure 10 - Overall Eco-Cost for LIB pouch cell	56

PENDING FOR EC APPROVAL

List of tables

Table 1 - Monetization conversion factor for PEF impact categories.....	21
Table 2 - Benchmark definition per Demonstrator.....	24
Table 3 - Comparative Review of Smart Textiles	30
Table 4 - Comparative Review of Lithium-based Battery Technologies.....	34
Table 5 - Impact Category Definitions for Environmental Footprint 3.1 (Adapted) V1.01.....	39
Table 6 - LCI of 1 kg rGO treated textile	40
Table 7 - Results of LCA (Environmental Footprint 3.1 (adapted) V1.01 / EF 3.1 normalization and weighting set).....	42
Table 8 - Main Input Distribution in percentage (%)	42
Table 9 - Eco-Cost results for rGO treated textile	46
Table 10 - Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of LIB pouch cell	51
Table 11 - Results of preliminary LCA with EF3.1 Method.....	53
Table 12 - Main Input Distribution in percentage (%).....	54
Table 13 - Eco-Cost results for LIB pouch cell	56
Table 14 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 1	68
Table 15 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 2	69
Table 16 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 1.....	71
Table 17 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 2.....	72
Table 18 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 1	73
Table 19 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 2	74
Table 20 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 3	75
Table 21 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 1	75
Table 22 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 2	76
Table 23 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 3	77
Table 24 - SimaPro evaluation rGO treated textile results with mPt, Part 1	79
Table 25 - SimaPro evaluation rGO treated textile results with mPt, Part 2	80
Table 26 - SimaPro evaluation LIB pouch cell results with mPt, Part 1.....	80
Table 27 - SimaPro evaluation LIB pouch cell results with mPt, Part 2.....	81
Table 28 - SimaPro evaluation LIB pouch cell results with mPt, Part 3.....	82

Abbreviations

2D	Two-dimensional
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CF	Carbon Footprint
CNTs	Carbon nanotubes
CVD	Chemical Vapor Deposition
EOl	End of Life
EU	European Union
FU	Functional Unit
GBMs	Graphene-based materials
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCO	Lithium Cobalt Oxide
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LCT	Life Cycle Thinking
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LIBs	Lithium-ion batteries
LiPF₆	Lithium Hexafluorophosphate
MVCs	Monetary Valuation Coefficients
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt
OPEX	Operational Costs
PEDOT:PSS	Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
rGO	Reduced graphene oxide
SCs	Supercapacitors
SETAC	The Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry

SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SiC	Silicon Carbide
SiNW	Silicon nanowires
SoA	State of the Art
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
TENGs	Triboelectric nanogenerator
TRACI	Tool for the Reduction and Assessment of Chemical and Other Environmental Impacts
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UV	Ultraviolet radiation
Wd	Wearable device
WP	Work Package

PENDING FOR EC APPROVAL

Executive summary

This Deliverable (D6.1) presents the methodological framework and preliminary results of the environmental and economic assessments conducted within WP6 – “Life cycle assessment, sustainability and ecodesign approach” of the GRAPHERGIA project. The report establishes the reference boundaries and functional units for the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) of the three GRAPHERGIA demonstrators, focusing on graphene-enabled technologies for energy harvesting, sensing, and storage.

The methodological approach follows ISO 14040/14044 standards for LCA and EN 60300-3-3 for LCC, ensuring consistency with Life Cycle Thinking and the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) principles. Environmental impacts were modelled using the Environmental Footprint 3.1 method, while economic performance was preliminarily evaluated through the Eco-Cost approach, translating environmental burdens into monetary terms to support early eco-design decisions.

A benchmarking framework has been defined to compare the performance of GRAPHERGIA demonstrators with conventional reference systems, based on functional equivalence. The defined benchmarks are:

Demonstrator #1: self-charging textile vs. conventional textile + external battery;

Demonstrator #2: self-powered sensor vs. wired aerospace sensor;

Demonstrator #3: LIB based on laser-derived graphene/Si anode vs. commercial batteries used in CubeSats

Preliminary results indicate that the integration of graphene-based materials offers significant potential to reduce environmental burdens and improve resource efficiency, although data gaps still limit the completeness of the current analysis—especially for demonstrators at early TRL stages. The final LCA and LCC, to be delivered in D6.2 (M42), will integrate experimental data and refined process inventories generated during the project, enabling a comprehensive sustainability evaluation.

Overall, this deliverable sets the baseline for the forthcoming assessments and provides a robust methodological foundation for evaluating the environmental and economic sustainability of graphene-based technologies developed in GRAPHERGIA.

1 Introduction

The environmental and economic impacts of fossil-based technologies are well-documented, and their progressive replacement with cleaner, more sustainable alternatives is essential for enabling a viable low-carbon future. In an increasingly energy-dependent world, the ability to harvest, store, and efficiently manage energy is becoming a critical priority, especially in emerging sectors such as wearable electronics, aerospace, and next-generation energy storage systems.

In this context, graphene and other two-dimensional (2D) materials have attracted growing interest due to their exceptional mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties, opening the door to a wide range of technological applications.

The GRAPHERGIA project aims to explore and validate these applications, developing new solutions such as self-powered textiles, structurally integrated sensors, and graphene-based lithium-ion batteries, with a particular focus on sustainability, cost-efficiency, and circularity from early development stages.

Building on this vision, GRAPHERGIA advances the understanding and practical use of graphene-based technologies, emphasizing their integration into real-world, sustainable solutions. A major objective is to investigate the potential of graphene for next-generation electronic textiles (e-textiles), an emerging field that merges smart materials, energy harvesting, and wearable innovation. Importantly, GRAPHERGIA contributes to and is aligned with the broader goals of the Graphene Flagship research initiative, one of the largest scientific projects ever funded by the European Union. Through this collaboration, the project supports the scaling up of graphene-enabled technologies while addressing critical challenges related to environmental performance, economic feasibility, and regulatory readiness.

This report presents a comprehensive evaluation of selected graphene-based technologies developed within the GRAPHERGIA project, with a focus on their environmental and economic performance. The assessment includes a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to quantify environmental impacts, a Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis to evaluate economic sustainability, and a cost feasibility study to assess the practical viability of implementing these solutions at scale.

By addressing both the scientific and sustainability challenges, GRAPHERGIA contributes to the broader goals of the European Green Deal and the transition to a circular and climate-neutral economy.

1.1 Description of the document

This Deliverable 6.1, *Preliminary LCA and LCC Assessment*, presents the first comprehensive evaluation of the environmental and economic performance of the technologies developed within the GRAPHERGIA project. It combines methodological definitions, preliminary results, and benchmarking analyses to establish the foundations for a fully integrated sustainability assessment in subsequent project stages.

The document outlines how Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Eco-Cost methodologies will be applied to the three project demonstrators:

1. **Demonstrator #1** – Self-charging textile for energy harvesting and storage (smart clothing and upholstery applications).
2. **Demonstrator #2** – Self-powered wireless sensor embedded in aerospace composite structures.
3. **Demonstrator #3** – Graphene-based lithium-ion battery module for space applications.

At this stage, the assessment process is still at an early phase. Since the development of the demonstrators will start later in the project (at M30), only preliminary LCA and Eco-Cost analyses have been performed for Demonstrators #1 and #3, based on available laboratory-scale data and partner inputs. As the current lab-scale process of Demonstrator #1 is also representative for Demonstrator #2, no LCA or LCC analyses have been conducted yet for this demonstrator. As technological progress continues and more representative process data become available, comprehensive LCA, LCC, and Eco-Cost analyses will be performed in the subsequent project phases.

The document details the methodological framework adopted for environmental and economic assessment, including goal and scope definition, data collection strategy, and modelling assumptions. The study applies ISO 14040/14044-compliant LCA and integrates an Eco-Cost monetisation approach to express environmental burdens in economic terms. While the overall framework for LCC is presented and harmonised with the LCA boundaries, no quantitative LCC has been performed at this preliminary stage, as the demonstrators are still under laboratory-scale development and cost structures are not yet representative of industrial conditions. The LCC analysis will be implemented in future project phases, once reliable cost data and process scale-up information become available.

Beyond methodology, the deliverable includes:

- A **state-of-the-art review** of graphene-based technologies and comparable systems (smart textiles, triboelectric nanogenerators, and lithium-ion batteries), providing contextual benchmarks for interpreting sustainability performance;

- **Preliminary LCA and Eco-Cost assessments** for selected demonstrators using SimaPro 10.2 and Ecoinvent 3.11;
- **Identification of environmental hotspots** and preliminary insights to guide eco-design decisions and future LCC implementation;
- A discussion of **limitations and future perspectives**, outlining data gaps, next steps for inventory refinement, and planned inclusion of end-of-life and social LCA analyses.

Overall, Deliverable 6.1 defines the methodological and analytical baseline for Task 6.1 (LCA) and Task 6.2 (LCC), supporting the integration of sustainability indicators into the technological development and eco-design strategy of GRAPHERGIA.

1.2 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

This deliverable is primarily associated with Work Package 6 (WP6) – Life Cycle Assessment, Sustainability and EcoDesign Approach, led by NTT, and contributes to the definition of the methodological and analytical framework for sustainability evaluation within GRAPHERGIA. It directly supports the activities of Tasks 6.1 and 6.2, while establishing the basis for future integration with Task 6.3 (Social LCA) and cross-linking with WP5 (Design, Manufacturing and Testing of Representative Technology Demonstrators).

WP6 – Life Cycle Assessment, Sustainability and EcoDesign Approach

- **Task 6.1 – Environmental Life Cycle Assessment**

D6.1 builds upon the methodological framework and preliminary inventory data developed under Task 6.1, which aims to quantify the environmental impacts associated with the synthesis, processing, and integration of graphene-based materials and components used in the project demonstrators.

At this stage, preliminary LCAs have been completed for Demonstrators #1 and #3, applying ISO 14040/14044 standards through SimaPro 10.2 and Ecoinvent 3.11. The analyses identify key environmental hotspots, enabling early guidance for eco-design and material optimization.

For Demonstrator #2, no LCA analysis has been conducted at this stage, as the current lab-scale process of Demonstrator #1 is considered representative for this demonstrator. The assessment for Demonstrator #2 will be carried out in later stages, once sufficient technological and process data specific to this application become available. The LCA framework established in this deliverable ensures consistency for future updates and integration of all demonstrators within a unified sustainability assessment structure.

- **Task 6.2 – Life Cycle Cost (LCC) and Cost-Feasibility**

Task 6.2 focuses on evaluating the economic sustainability and cost-effectiveness of GRAPHERGIA technologies.

In this preliminary phase, the deliverable introduces the methodological framework for environmental LCC, harmonized with the LCA system boundaries and ISO guidelines, but does not include quantitative LCC results, as the demonstrators are still at laboratory scale and detailed cost data are not yet representative of industrial conditions.

Instead, Eco-Cost analysis has been conducted as a complementary economic-environmental indicator, providing a first estimation of the monetary value associated with environmental prevention efforts.

The quantitative LCC modelling will be developed in future project phases, once process scale-up and cost structures are defined, allowing for more realistic life-cycle cost projections and comparison with conventional technologies.

- **Task 6.3 - Social LCA**

This task focuses on assessing the potential social and socio-economic impacts of GRAPHERGIA technologies along their life cycle. Data inputs for the S-LCA will include the environmental inventories (LCI) generated in Task 6.1 and the economic datasets developed under Task 6.2, ensuring methodological alignment and consistency across sustainability dimensions. The integration of these datasets within the SHDB framework will enable a comprehensive life-cycle sustainability perspective that connects environmental, economic, and social indicators. While Deliverable 6.1 focuses on the environmental (LCA) and economic (Eco-Cost and LCC) aspects, the preliminary results of the Social LCA activities conducted under Task 6.3 are reported separately in Deliverable D6.3 – Preliminary Social LCA Assessment.

Together, these deliverables form a coherent and complementary set of analyses supporting GRAPHERGIA's Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design approach and its integration of all three sustainability pillars into the development of graphene-based technologies.

Contribution to Other Work Packages

Deliverable 6.1 also provides relevant input to other work packages, particularly:

- **WP5 – Design, Manufacturing and Testing of Representative Demonstrators**

The sustainability insights derived from the LCA and Eco-Cost analyses will guide **Task 5.1** in the design and development of demonstrators, supporting material selection, process optimization, and eco-design decisions.

- **WP2–WP4 – Materials Synthesis and Processing**

Data collected from these WPs feed directly into the LCI development, ensuring the coherence of environmental and process data used in the assessments.

2 Methodology

2.1 Goal and scope

The preliminary environmental and economic assessment of the selected graphene-based demonstrators developed within the GRAPHERGIA project was carried out following a **Life Cycle Thinking (LCT)** approach, integrating LCA and LCC methodologies. These assessments are aligned with ISO 14040/14044 standards and supported by **eco-design principles** to guide the development of sustainable, efficient, and circular technologies.

The main objective of this study is to perform a preliminary sustainability evaluation of the GRAPHERGIA demonstrators by quantifying their environmental performance through LCA and translating these impacts into economic terms using the Eco-Cost methodology. The outcomes are intended to support early-stage eco-design decisions, identify environmental hotspots, and assess the potential scalability of the proposed innovations. Although the methodological framework for LCC is defined in this report, no quantitative LCC has been performed at this stage, as the demonstrators are still under laboratory development and cost data are not yet representative of industrial-scale production.

The assessment focuses on three demonstrators developed within **WP5**:

- **Demonstrator #1:** Self-charging textile system for energy harvesting and storage, implemented in both smart clothing (CS1) and smart upholstery applications (CS2) (**Figure 1**).
- **Demonstrator #2:** Self-powered wireless sensor embedded in aerospace composite structures for strain and temperature monitoring (**Figure 2**).
- **Demonstrator #3:** Graphene-based lithium-ion battery (LIB) module for space applications, tested on CubeSat platforms (**Figure 3**).

At this preliminary stage, LCA and Eco-Cost analyses have been carried out for Demonstrators #1 and #3, while Demonstrator #2 will be assessed in future project phases given that its current lab-scale process is represented by Demonstrator #1. The analyses adopt a **cradle-to-gate** system boundary, encompassing:

- Raw material extraction and processing
- Manufacturing and assembly
- Partial use-phase considerations (where relevant to functional performance and durability)

- Exclusion of end-of-life (EoL) scenarios at this stage, due to limited data availability - Where possible, the assessment of EoL scenarios will be carried out and presented in the final version of this work, due at M42.

The **Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)** data were compiled from a combination of:

- Experimental inputs provided by WP2–WP5,
- Data from technology developers and demonstrator partners,
- Secondary data from scientific literature and databases,
- Extrapolations based on known industrial processes for comparable products.

The LCA was conducted using SimaPro 10.2 and the Ecoinvent 3.11 database, following a cradle-to-gate approach with selective inclusion of use-phase parameters where significant to the overall environmental profile.

In parallel, the deliverable includes a comprehensive state-of-the-art and benchmarking analysis of comparable technologies in the fields of smart textiles, triboelectric nanogenerators, and lithium-ion batteries. This contextual review supports the interpretation of results and helps identify innovation gaps, providing a solid foundation for subsequent LCA, LCC, and Eco-Cost integration in GRAPHERGIA’s sustainability strategy.

Overall, this goal and scope definition supports Tasks 6.1 and 6.2, contributing to design optimization, data harmonization, and the overall sustainability roadmap of the GRAPHERGIA project.

Figure 1 - Demonstrator #1: Self-charging textile for energy harvesting and storage

Figure 2 - Demonstrator #2: Self-powered wireless sensor embedded in aerospace composite structures

Figure 3 - Demonstrator #3: Graphene-based LIBs battery module for space applications

2.2 Methodology for Life Cycle Assessment

The LCA is a standardized methodology for evaluating the environmental impacts associated with products, services, or organizations throughout their entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. It is internationally regulated by the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards.

The Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) defines LCA as “a process to evaluate the environmental burdens associated with a product, process, or activity by identifying and quantifying energy and materials used and wastes released to the environment, and to assess the impact of those energy and material uses and releases to the environment” [1].

As illustrated in **Figure 4**, the LCA framework consists of four main phases:

- **Goal and Scope Definition:** This phase defines the purpose of the study, the target audience, the system boundaries, and the functional unit (FU). The FU is a key concept that serves as a reference point for all input and output flows within the system. It ensures consistency and comparability across different scenarios and alternatives [2].
- **Life Cycle Inventory (LCI):** In this phase, data are collected and quantified regarding material and energy inputs and outputs, including emissions to air, water, and soil. The inventory provides the quantitative basis for the impact assessment [3].
- **Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA):** The LCIA phase interprets the inventory data into environmental impact indicators, grouped into categories such as climate change, eutrophication, acidification, and resource depletion. The objective is to understand the potential environmental consequences of the identified flows [3].
- **Life Cycle Interpretation:** This final phase critically analyses the results from the LCI and LCIA to draw conclusions consistent with the initial goals. It identifies key impact areas, evaluates uncertainties, and provides recommendations to support environmental improvements of the system under study [2].

Figure 4- Stages of an LCA framework (ISO 14040)

2.3 Methodology for Life Cycle Costing

Conducting a LCC analysis within the broader Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) framework requires harmonised methodological choices that are consistent with the LCA. Therefore, the approach adopted in this study follows the principles outlined in ISO 14040 for environmental LCA, while also referring to the guidance provided in the European standard EN 60300-3-3: *Dependability Management – Part 3-3: Application Guide – Life Cycle Costing*.

As illustrated in **Figure 4**, LCC follows the same general structure as LCA, comprising: Goal and scope definition, LCI analysis of cost flows, Cost impact assessment and Interpretation of results.

This alignment ensures consistency across both environmental and economic assessments, allowing the integration of cost-related decisions into early-stage eco-design strategies and sustainability evaluations.

There are different approaches to LCC, each varying in scope and cost coverage [4]:

- **Conventional LCC:**

Focuses on direct economic costs borne by a single actor (e.g., the producer or end-user). It excludes external costs such as environmental or social impacts and is typically used for internal budgeting or investment planning.

- **Environmental LCC:**

Accounts for the full spectrum of costs incurred by all relevant stakeholders throughout the product life cycle. This includes direct and anticipated external costs, such as regulatory fees, carbon pricing, or extended producer responsibility charges. Environmental LCC is conducted in parallel with LCA, sharing the same goal, scope, and system boundaries, thus enabling a consistent sustainability analysis.

- **Societal LCC:**

Expands on environmental LCC by also monetising environmental and social externalities (e.g., health impacts, loss of biodiversity, noise pollution). This approach provides a broader societal perspective and is often used in public policy or infrastructure planning where long-term societal welfare is the objective.

In the context of the GRAPHERGIA project, the environmental LCC approach has been prioritised. This allows the project to assess the economic feasibility of each demonstrator while integrating projected regulatory trends (e.g., carbon taxation, end-of-life charges) and aligning the cost analysis with environmental impact findings from the LCA. Cost inventories are developed for each life cycle stage, from material extraction and component manufacturing to product assembly and partial use phase. End-of-life costs are not included in this preliminary study but will be addressed in subsequent phases as data become available.

This methodology directly supports Task 6.2, feeding into the broader evaluation of technological scalability, cost-competitiveness, and innovation-driven cost reduction potential across the graphene-based solutions being developed in GRAPHERGIA.

2.4 Methodology for Eco-Cost

The Eco-Costs methodology is a prevention-based, LCA derived monetary indicator developed to quantify the environmental burden of products, processes, or services in terms of the marginal costs required to reduce emissions and resource depletion to a sustainable “no effect” level, consistent with the Earth’s carrying capacity [5][6]. Unlike market prices, which reflect supply-demand dynamics, eco-costs represent virtual prevention costs, the theoretical expenditure needed to avoid environmental damage [5].

The method consolidates marginal prevention costs across three principal impact categories, material depletion, fossil energy consumption, and toxic emissions, into a single monetary value expressed in euros per FU [5][7]. Marginal prevention costs are calculated using best-available abatement technologies and policy benchmarks, and updated periodically to reflect changes in environmental targets and technology costs [5].

By translating multiple environmental indicators into a uniform monetary metric, the eco-costs approach enables transparent comparison between alternative design options or production pathways, supporting decision-making in eco-design, supply chain optimisation, and policy evaluation [9]. This facilitates “de-linking” economic growth from environmental degradation, and is particularly relevant for circular economy business models, where eco-costs can assess the environmental performance of reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling strategies [7].

The methodology is fully LCA compliant under ISO 14040/14044 guidelines for monetary valuation of environmental impacts [9]. It has been applied in both business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) contexts for sustainability communication, product

benchmarking, and ecolabelling, helping bridge the gap between technical LCA outputs and stakeholder decision-making [11]. In the GRAPHERGIA context, eco-costs can serve as a harmonised quantitative indicator for assessing and communicating the environmental performance of graphene-based energy harvesting and storage devices across their full life cycle.

In the scientific literature, the term Eco-Cost denotes the external environmental costs associated with emissions and resource consumption, which are typically not accounted for in conventional market pricing. It reflects the theoretical monetary value required to prevent or offset environmental degradation, thereby serving as a proxy for the shadow price of environmental impacts. This conceptual framework is consistent with the methodologies outlined in the key sources referenced in this analysis.

- Amadei et al. (2021) [12] present an extensive analysis of monetary valuation within LCA, discussing the different conceptual bases used to assign Monetary Valuation Coefficients (MVCs) to environmental impact categories. These coefficients can be established through approaches such as damage cost estimation, abatement cost calculations, or methods based on individuals' willingness to pay.
- Smith et al. (2020) [13] in their study for the European Commission, introduce a harmonized set of monetization factors aligned with the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) framework. These values, expressed in €/unit of impact, are designed to enhance policy-relevant assessments of environmental costs at the EU scale, covering impact categories such as climate change, human toxicity, particulate matter, and resource consumption (**Table 1**).

Impact category	Unit	Smith et al. (2020) [13]	Amadei et al. (2021) [12]	Average
		Monetisation factor €/unit		
Acidification	Mole of H ⁺ eq	0.39 €	0.38 €	0.38 €
Climate Change	kg CO ₂ eq	0.12 €	0.07 €	0.09 €
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	0.00004 €	0.00004 €	0.00004€
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	2.16 €	2.14 €	2.15 €
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	3.61 €	7.26 €	5.44 €
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Mole of N eq	- €	- €	- €
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	1,020,000.00 €	887,000.00 €	953,500.00 €
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	184,000.00 €	174,000.00 €	179,000.00 €
Ionising radiation, human health	kBq U235 eq	0.0014 €	0.23 €	0.12 €
Land Use	Pt	0.002 €	0.0002 €	0.0011 €
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	35.30 €	60.60 €	47.95 €

Particulate matter	Disease incidences	883,000.00 €	872,000.00 €	877,500.00 €
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	kg NMVOC eq	1.34 €	3.84 €	2.59 €
Resource use, fossils	MJ	0.001 €	0.01 €	0.01 €
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	1.85 €	1.81 €	1.83 €
Water use	m ³ world equiv	0.01 €	0.01 €	0.01 €

Table 1 - Monetization conversion factor for PEF impact categories

In this study, LCA outcomes were converted into monetary terms by applying specific factors (€/unit of impact). The resulting values were then aggregated across all impact categories to calculate the overall Eco-Cost per FU. The monetisation factors derived from [13] and [12] were applied directly to the midpoint impact results obtained through the Environmental Footprint 3.1 (adapted) V1.01 (hereinafter referred to as **EF3.1 Method**). Each impact category result (expressed in its native unit) was multiplied by the corresponding PEF-based conversion factor (€/unit impact) and then normalised to the defined FU of the system under study. The monetised values were subsequently aggregated across all relevant impact categories to obtain the total Eco-Cost per FU, expressed in euro. This approach ensures consistency with ISO 14040/14044 principles and enables a transparent translation of environmental burdens into economic terms. The Eco-Cost method relies exclusively on LCA outcomes and is not integrated within the LCC framework. It should be noted that negative eco-cost values were normalized to zero in cases where an environmental category yielded a negative result, since such outcomes do not represent actual environmental burdens and therefore do not entail any associated prevention costs.

2.5 Limitations of the Study

As D6.1 represents a preliminary assessment, several limitations affect the completeness and robustness of the results. These limitations are primarily related to the development stage of the GRAPHERGIA demonstrators, the availability of reliable data, and the scope of the analyses performed to date.

The main limitations can be summarised as follows:

- **Data availability and representativeness**

The demonstrators are currently under laboratory-scale development, and many process parameters are still being optimised. Consequently, several inventory inputs rely on experimental estimates, literature data, or extrapolations from similar industrial processes. As such, the datasets may not fully capture the variability or efficiency expected in future upscaled production.

- **Incomplete coverage of demonstrators**

Preliminary LCA and Eco-Cost analyses have been performed only for Demonstrators #1 and #3, as sufficient data were available to enable meaningful modelling. The analysis of Demonstrator #2 will be conducted at a later stage, since the laboratory-scale experimental process is similar to that of Demonstrator #1. Specifically, both demonstrators follow the same main processing steps:

- Spraying of graphene oxide (GO) dispersion on the fabric surface,
- Drying of the GO-treated fabric, and
- Irradiation of the GO-treated fabric for in-situ reduced graphene oxide (rGO) growth.

The only difference lies in the type of substrate used: in the case of Demonstrator #2, carbon-fabric materials are employed. The process for the production of GO-treated and rGO-treated fabrics is illustrated in **Figure 5** of Chapter “4.1 Life Cycle Assessment of Demonstrator #1: Data Analysis for Smart Textiles.”

- **Absence of quantitative LCC results**

Although the LCC framework has been defined in this deliverable, no quantitative LCC analysis has been conducted at this stage. Given the current maturity level of the technologies, cost data would not be representative of real production or market conditions. Quantitative cost modelling will be developed in subsequent project stages, when upscaling and design optimisation allow for more accurate cost estimations.

- **End-of-Life (EoL) considerations**

End-of-life scenarios were not included in this preliminary phase due to the early TRL of the technologies and the lack of EoL data for graphene-based components. However, where possible, EoL assessments will be incorporated and presented in the final version of this work, due at M42, to provide a more comprehensive life cycle perspective.

- **Use-phase assumptions**

At this stage, no quantitative assessment of the use phase has been included, as the operational behaviour and lifetime performance of the demonstrators are still under evaluation. Nevertheless, use-phase modelling may be integrated in the final version of this study (M42), particularly for applications where operational performance and energy efficiency are expected to significantly influence the overall environmental profile (e.g., energy storage and textile demonstrators).

Despite these limitations, the analyses conducted in this deliverable establish a solid methodological foundation and deliver valuable early insights into the sustainability performance of GRAPHERGIA technologies. The results will be progressively refined throughout the project as

data availability improves, supporting continuous eco-design optimisation and integration with LCC and S-LCA results in upcoming deliverables.

2.6 Future Perspectives

Building on the preliminary results and methodological framework established in this deliverable, the next phases of the GRAPHERGIA project will focus on refining and expanding the sustainability evaluation of the developed demonstrators through several key directions.

First, as the technologies advance and the demonstrators reach higher TRLs, more detailed and reliable process-level inventory data will become available. This will enable the development of updated and more representative LCAs and LCCs, reducing reliance on proxies or laboratory-scale assumptions and strengthening the robustness and accuracy of the environmental and economic assessments.

Second, the analysis will be extended to include EoL scenarios, particularly for energy storage components and e-textile systems. Specific attention will be given to potential reuse, recycling, and recovery routes for graphene-based materials (GBMs) and associated polymers. Incorporating these aspects will allow the completion of cradle-to-grave system boundaries and support the identification of circularity opportunities, in line with the project's objectives and the European Green Deal targets.

Furthermore, the eco-design strategy (Task 5.1 & Task 6.4) will continue to be informed by the LCA and LCC results, fostering an iterative design improvement process aimed at minimising environmental burdens while maximising functional performance. Particular focus will be placed on energy harvesting and storage efficiency, as well as on user-phase durability metrics such as washability, stretchability, and power density retention over time.

Finally, the project will pursue comparative benchmarking against existing commercial solutions (e.g., conventional batteries, wearable devices, and aerospace sensors) to quantify the added value and innovation potential of the graphene-based technologies developed in GRAPHERGIA, from both environmental and economic perspectives.

These future developments will ensure a progressively more comprehensive and data-driven understanding of the sustainability performance of the GRAPHERGIA outcomes, contributing to their industrial readiness, circularity, and long-term market viability.

2.7 Benchmarking Definition and Reference Systems

In the context of WP6, benchmarking is defined as the comparison of the environmental and economic performance of GRAPHERGIA demonstrators against a relevant reference system (benchmark product) performing an equivalent function. In line with ISO 14040/14044 standards

and EN 60300-3-3 guidelines for LCC, the benchmarking process follows a functional equivalence approach, meaning that both the GRAPHERGIA demonstrator and the benchmark system are evaluated based on a common FU, ensuring comparability and methodological consistency across the two sustainability dimensions (**Table 2**).

Demonstrator	Application domain	Benchmark product/system	Functional Unit (FU)	Benchmarking rationale
#1 – Self charging textile for energy harvesting and storage	Smart clothing / upholstery for energy harvesting and storage	Conventional textile integrated with external Li-ion battery or power bank	1 kg of functional textile capable of storing and delivering 1 Wh (or kWh) of energy	Enables comparison between integrated (graphene-based) and traditional textile–battery systems in terms of embodied energy and material intensity.
#2 – Self powered wireless sensor embedded in aerospace composite structures	Self-powered wireless sensing for aerospace composite structures	Conventional wired aerospace sensor module (strain/temperature)	1 functional sensor unit providing equivalent sensing performance (per measurement channel)	Allows assessment of the environmental and cost benefits of autonomous, graphene-based sensing compared to standard powered or wired systems.
#3 – Graphene based LIBs battery module for space applications	Energy storage for CubeSat and small satellite applications	Standard lithium-ion battery module used in CubeSats	1 kWh of storage capacity (for 20 units as annual production rate) – 20 units of 0.05 kWh per CubeSat	Provides consistent comparison with literature data and existing LCA/LCC datasets for conventional LIBs in aerospace or high-performance electronics.

Table 2 - Benchmark definition per Demonstrator

By defining a specific benchmark product and functional unit for each demonstrator, the project ensures that the comparative analyses (LCA, LCC, and S-LCA) are functionally equivalent, transparent, and reproducible.

This benchmarking framework enables a harmonised evaluation of performance improvements and sustainability benefits introduced by GRAPHERGIA technologies, supporting the project's Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approach and aligning with the broader objectives of the European Green Deal and circular economy transition.

3 GRAPHERGIA technology

The following sections present a state-of-the-art (SoA) review of the key technologies, materials, and processes underpinning the demonstrators developed within the GRAPHERGIA project.

The analysis focuses on recent advances in fields such as energy harvesting and storage, flexible and wearable electronics, and sensor integration, which are essential for enabling the functionality and sustainability of the proposed solutions. This overview supports the technical validation and sustainability assessment activities by providing benchmark data and identifying current limitations and opportunities in the field.

3.1 Graphene

Graphene continues to attract significant attention across a wide range of technological domains due to its exceptional physical and chemical properties. Structurally, it is a 2D allotrope of carbon composed of a single atomic layer arranged in a hexagonal (honeycomb) lattice. Each carbon atom is covalently bonded to three others via sp^2 hybridization, forming strong in-plane σ -bonds. The delocalized π -electrons above and below the basal plane endow graphene with remarkable electronic characteristics, including high electrical conductivity [11][15].

Graphene also combines other extraordinary attributes: mechanical strength (over 100 times stronger than steel by weight), high elasticity and flexibility, excellent thermal conductivity, ultraviolet and flame resistance, chemical stability, atomic thinness, impermeability to gases, and a large specific surface area. Despite being only one atom thick, it remains optically transparent [16][17][18].

These multifunctional properties make graphene an ideal candidate for numerous applications, including: flexible and wearable electronics, supercapacitors and lithium-based batteries, transparent conductive films, composites and coatings, biosensors and biomedical devices, photovoltaics and solar cells, conductive inks and sensors, aerospace, automotive, and naval components, concrete, cement additives, and emerging contaminant removal [16][19][18][17][20][21]. **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.**[22][23][24][26][27][28].

LCA and LCC are critical methodologies for assessing the environmental and economic sustainability of GBMs, and the field has attracted much research attention. LCA studies highlight that synthesis routes significantly affect environmental performance. For instance, chemical reduction using toxic agents like hydrazine introduces high human and ecotoxicity, while ultrasonic methods consume substantial energy and solvents [29][30]. Even “green” precursors, such as biomass, do not guarantee lower impact due to energy-intensive processing.

Disparities in methodology, such as system boundaries or FUs, complicate comparisons, underlining the need for standardized LCA frameworks. LCC complements LCA by quantifying total life-cycle costs, including raw materials, energy, labour, equipment, and waste management.

Together, LCA and LCC enable SSbD, aligned with the European Commission's goals to integrate safety, circularity, and sustainability into early-stage material innovation [31].

3.2 Triboelectric Nanogenerators

Recent advancements in TENGs have highlighted graphene and its derivatives as highly promising materials for improving energy harvesting performance, enabling scalable production, and adding multifunctional capabilities. These developments form a key component of the GRAPHERGIA project, specifically within Demonstrators #1 and #2.

TENGs are a class of energy harvesting devices that convert mechanical energy, such as motion, vibration, or pressure, into electrical energy through a combination of contact electrification (triboelectric effect) and electrostatic induction. First introduced by Wang and his team in 2012 [32], TENGs have since emerged as a promising solution for powering small-scale, self-sustaining electronics, especially in the context of wearable technology, environmental sensors, and the IoTs. The IoTs is a dynamic network of interconnected smart devices, ranging from sensors to industrial machines, that collect, share, and process data in real time to enable automation and intelligent decision-making across diverse sectors [33][34]. As highlighted by Ganguly and Sengupta (2024) [35], the integration of advanced materials like graphene further enhances IoT systems by improving sensor sensitivity, flexibility, and energy efficiency.

Graphene's exceptional electrical conductivity, mechanical flexibility, and large specific surface area make it an ideal candidate for improving charge transfer and surface contact efficiency in TENGs.

Ahmed et al. (2017) [36] conducted a cradle to grave environmental LCA and techno-economic analysis of two TENGs designs: a high-efficiency Model A and a lower-efficiency Model B. The study evaluated performance across production, use, and EoL phases, and benchmarked results against photovoltaic technologies including crystalline silicon, organic, and perovskite cells.

Model A achieved a global warming potential of approximately 2.75 kg CO₂eq per kWh, markedly lower than Model B at about 9.8 kg CO₂eq per kWh, and far below the 30–80 kg CO₂eq per kWh typically reported for crystalline silicon PV.

From a life cycle costing perspective, Model A was also more competitive, with an estimated production cost of about 0.17 USD/W compared to 0.62 USD/W for Model B. The environmental hotspots for Model B were linked to its higher acrylic content, which drove up both Carbon Footprint (CF) and energy demand, and to greater energy consumption during manufacturing.

EoL considerations showed that the acrylic component could be recycled or reused, and its combustion would not release toxic gases.

By integrating both environmental and economic indicators, the study demonstrated that targeted material choices and process optimisations could significantly reduce the life cycle impacts and costs of TENGs technology, positioning high-efficiency designs like Model A as more sustainable energy harvesting solutions.

Hatta et al. (2021) [37] provided a comprehensive review of graphene-based TENGs, focusing on material synthesis methods, device architectures, and emerging applications. They emphasized that graphene enhances the output performance of TENGs due to its high electron mobility and ability to form conformal contacts with various surfaces. Building on this, Xie et al. (2025) [38] demonstrated recent innovations in graphene-based electrodes for TENGs, where hybrid and multilayered configurations have significantly improved energy conversion efficiency. These innovations are particularly relevant for wearable electronics, where device flexibility and low weight are crucial.

Xiong et al. (2023) [39] further explored the scalability of graphene-enabled TENGs by developing textile-based systems that can be produced through spinning, winding, and knitting techniques. These graphene textile TENGs not only harvest biomechanical energy efficiently but also offer the potential for integration into smart clothing for human motion sensing and self-powered wearable devices (Wd).

Overall, the integration of graphene into TENGs design is a major step toward scalable, flexible, and high-performance energy harvesters. These developments align with broader goals of sustainability and self-sufficient electronics, indicating that graphene-enhanced TENGs could play a significant role in next-generation energy and sensor systems.

3.3 Smart Textiles for Wearable Energy and Graphene Applications

Smart textiles, or e-textiles, are innovative fabrics integrated with electronics, such as sensors, actuators, or energy systems, designed for flexibility, comfort, and real-time interactivity. These materials are pivotal in advancing sustainable digital health, energy-autonomous IoTs systems, and circular wearable design strategies [40][41][42][43][44][45][46][47][48].

Numerous studies, including reviews and case analyses, have examined the growing research into advanced technologies applied to textiles, with a wide range of applications spanning fields such as sports, healthcare, and beyond. In this context, smart textiles have emerged as a key area of innovation, where graphene plays a fundamental role, particularly in enabling integrated energy functions. Its unique electrical, thermal, and mechanical properties make it highly compatible with

emerging technologies such as TENGs, wearable electronics, and the IoTs. This integration is also reflected in the objectives of the GRAPHERGIA project, which explores the use of graphene in textile-based energy systems within the framework of European research and innovation. Specifically, GRAPHERGIA Demonstrator #1, comprising CS1 smart clothing and CS2 smart textile for upholstery, is designed to showcase the practical implementation of these graphene-enhanced energy solutions.

While numerous LCA studies exist for conventional textiles, there is still a significant gap in the literature regarding the environmental impacts of smart textiles. Recent research has also begun to explore LCA methodologies to evaluate the sustainability of these emerging technologies. This area of investigation aligns closely with the objectives of the preliminary deliverable, which specifically aims to assess both the LCA and LCC of graphene-based smart textile solutions.

Van der Velden et al. (2015) [46] carried out a “cradle to grave” life cycle assessment of the “Vibe-ing” smart textile, a vibration therapy garment, using SimaPro v8 and the Eco-costs/Value Ratio (EVR) method as developed by Vogtländer et al., 2010 [8]. Designed for a total service life of five years treating five patients for one year each the product showed total impacts of €45.1 eco-costs ($\approx 45.1 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{eq}$). The production stage dominated the footprint, accounting for 74% of the total, largely due to the electronics, particularly the high-silver content conductive yarn, and to a lesser extent the Merino wool textile. The use phase contributed 24% of the impacts, driven mainly by patient facility transport, while end-of-life represented just 3%. Through targeted eco-design interventions, such as replacing silver with copper, substituting Merino wool with acrylic, reducing the amount of conductive material, and extending product lifespan, the study demonstrated that overall environmental impacts could be reduced by more than a quarter.

Azani et al. (2024) [41] explore the integration and lifecycle durability of e-textiles, emphasizing the importance of washability, biocompatibility, and recyclability. They advocate for modular electronics and cradle-to-cradle strategies, essential for environmentally compliant design.

Dulal et al. (2024) [45] present a sustainable design framework for fully inkjet-printed smart wearable e-textiles, combining natural, renewable substrates with environmentally benign conductive materials. The garments are fabricated on Tencel™/Lyocell, produced in a closed-loop process with approximately 99% recovery of water and solvents, and printed using water-based inks containing graphene or PEDOT:PSS. A “cradle to grave” LCA, conducted to ISO 14040/14044 standards and using ReCiPe 2016 indicators, shows that the graphene-based electrode achieves the lowest climate change impact, just $0.037 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{eq}$, representing a 97.5% reduction compared to a conventional metal/solvent-based electrode. It also records the lowest terrestrial acidification, human carcinogenic toxicity, and roughly half the water consumption of the reference design.

EoL performance is addressed through soil burial biodegradation tests, where the graphene electrode lost nearly 48% of its weight and around 98% of its tensile strength within four months,

indicating significant microbial breakdown. Natural fibres and graphene promoted diverse bacterial and fungal activity in the soil, while PEDOT:PSS tended to support primarily fungal growth. By uniting biodegradable substrates, solvent-free conductive inks, precision inkjet printing with minimal waste, and measurable degradability, the study demonstrates a pathway towards wearable electronics that are aligned with emerging LCA frameworks and closed-loop material cycles.

Zhu et al. (2021) [47] demonstrate graphene-based textile antennas and sensors, capable of wireless communication and environmental sensing. Their study points to the feasibility of self-powered IoT garments, given optimized low-power consumption electronics.

Zhu et al. (2025) [48] highlight that smart clothing, while innovative, faces major sustainability issues due to complex textile, electronics combinations that are hard to recycle. The authors propose a circular EcoDesign framework, focused on extending product life, enabling reuse and repair, improving recycling and biodegradation, and adding digital traceability to guide low-carbon, sustainable smart clothing development.

The LCA focused report (only two studies in the literature provide quantified sustainability assessments for smart clothing, using different approaches, **Table 3**) identifies major environmental burdens during raw material acquisition (especially silver inks, carbon nanostructures) and coating processes (e.g., electroless plating, screen printing). EoL challenges persist due to the hybrid nature of textile-electronics interfaces.

Reference	Technology-Materials	LCA Data (CO ₂ eq)	Biodegradability, EoL	Sustainability Strategies
Dulal et al., 2024 – [45] SWEET platform	Fully inkjet-printed e-textile on Tencel™/Lyocell; water-based inks with graphene and PEDOT:PSS	Graphene electrode: 0.037 kg CO ₂ eq (≈40× lower than metal/solvent-based electrode)	Weight loss ≈48% and tensile strength loss ≈98% after 4 months in soil burial test	Biodegradable substrate from closed-loop process (≈99% recovery water/solvent), high-precision inkjet printing (reduced waste, low energy), non-toxic water-based conductive inks replacing non-biodegradable metals
van der Velden et al., 2015 – [46] Vibe-ing smart textile	Merino wool + silver conductive yarn (Elektrisola) + electronic components	Total eco-costs: €45.1 ≈ 45.1 kg CO ₂ eq; Production €33.2 (74%), Use €10.6	Estimated 5-year service life, shared use among multiple patients; disposed of as	Material substitution (wool → acrylic –22% total, silver → copper –33% total), reduction of conductive material (–36%), removal of non-functional parts (–18%), alternative knitting

		(24%), End-of-life €1.3 (3%)	mixed municipal waste	techniques (-14%), extending service life by +50% (-33%)
--	--	---------------------------------	--------------------------	---

Table 3 - Comparative Review of Smart Textiles

3.4 Lithium-ion Batteries: Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Costing and Eco-Costs

In this context, lithium-based batteries represent an emerging and strategically important technology, whose performance and capabilities can be significantly enhanced through the integration of graphene materials. Graphene's exceptional electrical conductivity, mechanical strength, and high surface area contribute to improving energy density, charge-discharge rates, and overall battery lifespan. Within the framework of this study, particular emphasis is placed on aerospace applications, with a focus on Demonstrator #3, which involves implementation in a CubeSats satellite platform.

The transition to a climate neutral, resource efficient and socially sustainable energy system lies at the heart of the European Green Deal. In this context, advanced battery technologies are critical enablers for the decarbonisation of transport, grid stability, and renewable energy storage. The GRAPHERGIA project, funded under Horizon Europe, aims to unlock the potential of graphene-enhanced energy storage systems by advancing the integration of graphene and other 2D materials in sustainable battery chemistries.

LIBs remain the most widespread electrochemical storage solution due to their high energy density and broad industrial maturity. However, concerns over their environmental footprint, lifecycle cost, and ethical sourcing of raw materials have driven significant research into alternative chemistries and materials including graphene-enhanced cells.

This report provides a structured comparison of state-of-the-art literature evaluating the LCA, LCC and Eco-Cost of lithium-based battery technologies. Most of the existing literature is primarily concerned with the applications of LIBs in the automotive sector. It integrates peer-reviewed studies and technical reviews on established chemistries such as Nickel Manganese Cobalt (NMC), Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP), and Lithium Cobalt Oxide (LCO), as well as emerging options including graphite-graphene-based electrode. Emphasis is placed on GHG per FU (typically per kWh), EoL scenarios, and integration of circular economy strategies.

This comparative synthesis supports the GRAPHERGIA project's ambition to position graphene-based batteries within a sustainability-driven framework, aligning with EU targets for ethical supply chains, long-term recyclability, and net-zero carbon mobility.

According to Passerini et al. 2024 [49], the production phase of LIBs, particularly electrode preparation and cell assembly in dry-room environments, accounts for the largest share of environmental impacts, with high energy consumption and associated greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, the extraction and refining of critical raw materials such as lithium, cobalt, and nickel contribute significantly to resource depletion, human toxicity, and ecosystem damage indicators. Typical values reported in literature and confirmed by the authors for 1 kWh of LIB storage capacity include:

- Global Warming Potential (GWP): ~100–150 kg CO₂eq.
- Cumulative Energy Demand (CED): ~500–600 MJ
- High scores in resource depletion, particularly for cobalt and lithium.

The use phase tends to have a relatively minor environmental footprint compared to production, especially when powered by renewable electricity. However, performance degradation and short service lives can indirectly increase the overall impact per FU.

The EoL stage presents both a challenge and an opportunity. Currently, less than 10% of LIBs are effectively recycled, primarily due to technological and logistical barriers. The report highlights two main recycling pathways:

- Pyrometallurgical processing, involving high-temperature melting to recover metals, is widely used but energy-intensive.
- Hydrometallurgical methods, based on chemical leaching, are more selective and energy-efficient but require complex solvent handling.

These processes aim to recover cobalt, lithium, nickel, and other strategic elements, but are often limited by low yields, cross-contamination, and economic non-viability for certain battery chemistries. Aligned with the EU Battery Regulation (2023/1542) [50], future battery systems will be subject to:

- Mandatory recycled content thresholds (e.g., 16% cobalt, 6% lithium by 2031),
- Digital battery passports for traceability,
- Design for disassembly principles to facilitate material recovery.

In this context, LCA is not only a diagnostic tool but also a design driver, encouraging circular material flows and more efficient production practices. For GRAPHERGIA, these insights are

particularly relevant as the project explores the integration of graphene and advanced materials into smart textile-based energy systems, where sustainability must be embedded from the outset.

In the scientific literature, several review articles compile data on LCA, LCC, recycling scenarios, and EoL strategies for LIBs [57][56][70][73]. These reviews provide a solid foundation for identifying benchmarks relevant to the GRAPHERGIA project, which investigates the application of LIBs in CubeSat satellites.

Among these reviews, particular attention has been given to those focusing on LIBs and their GWP, as well as studies addressing EoL strategies.

To provide an immediate and structured overview, **Table 4** summarizes a selection of representative studies (among many others available in the literature). Presented in chronological order, these works highlight the technological developments, production methods, and assessment approaches applied to LIBs. Specifically, they analyse environmental impacts through LCA, with attention to system boundary definition, choice of FU, and potential recycling and reuse pathways. While most of these studies emphasize LCA-based evaluations, fewer contributions focus on LCC, eco-cost, and EoL strategies. Nevertheless, together they significantly enrich the knowledge base in this field and offer insights applicable to the GRAPHERGIA project.

Table 4 summarizes key data from a selection of recent publications on LIBs, graphene-based, focusing on LCA and LCC. Data sources include peer-reviewed studies selected, conducted between 2010 and 2025.

Reference	Battery Type	FU	System Boundary	Impact Categories - LCIA Method	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq)	LCC / Eco-Costs	Observations
Zackrisson et al., 2010 [51]	LIBs (LiFePO ₄)	1 kWh	Cradle to grave	GWP, ADP, toxicity (qualitative)	/	/	Water-based solvents more sustainable; internal efficiency crucial
Yu et al., 2014 [52]	LIB vs NiMH	1 battery life cycle	Cradle to grave	Eco-indicator 99 (qualitative)	Qualitative only	/	Recycling and increased battery life reduce impact
Zackrisson et al., 2016 [53]	LIBs-Air	1 kWh (projected use)	Cradle to grave	GWP, ADP, toxicity	~1.3 (prototipe)	/	Production dominates; future improvements may shift impacts
Liang et al., 2017 [54]	LIBs	1 battery pack (1000 kW h)	Partial	CO ₂ eq assembly only	12.7	/	CO ₂ eq for assembly stage only; very low value, likely partial scope

Ellingsen et al., 2017 [55]	LIBs	1 kWh	Cradle to gate	GWP	38–356	/	Large GHG variability based on methods & assumptions (review)
Peters et al., 2017 [57]	General LIB	1 Wh	Varies	GWP	110 g CO ₂ eq	/	review focus on battery production (LCI)
Wu et al., 2018 [72]	LIBs with three anode types: Li-metal, Si-nanowire, Graphite	1 kWh	Cradle to gate	TRACI 2.1 & CED	Lithium metal: 344.3; Silicon nanowire: 278.7; Graphite: 244.5	/	Comparative LCA of different anode chemistries. Lithium metal shows the highest GWP and energy demand; graphite the lowest.
Peters & Weil, 2018 [57]	LIBs (LFP, NCA (avg.))	1 kWh	Cradle to gate	GWP, ADP, CED	~150–200	/	Review, modelling affects results more than chemistry
Raugei & Winfield, 2019 [58]	LIBs (LMO, LFP, NCA, NCM)	1 kWh	Cradle to grave incl. recycling	GWP (IPCC)	76.1–70.7 (with EoL)	/	Hydro recycling reduces CO ₂ ; graphite recovery adds benefit
Dai et al., 2019 [59]	LIBs (NMC111)	1 kWh	Cradle to gate	GWP (IPCC)	72.9	/	Comparative chemistry focus
Cedras, 2020 [60]	Not specified	Per pack (estimated kWh)	Not specified	GWP	~130	Partial	Focus on automotive sector (review)
Lima et al., 2021 [61]	LIB (vs. VRFB)	1 MWh of electricity (AC) over 20 years	Not specified	ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H)	95	Partial	LIB has +52.2% acidification and +41.7% PM over VRFB
Sadhukhan et al., 2021 [62]	LIBs (LCO, NMC, LFP)	1 kWh	Cradle to cradle	ReCiPe Midpoint Hierarchical (M) (H), CML	6.7 - 8.1 - 1.7	/	Full LCSA framework; climate impact hotspots are phosphorous white liquid > copper cathode > anode graphite
Chen et al., 2022 [63]	LIBs (electric veicles)	1 kWh	Cradle to cradle	GWP (IPCC), scenario analysis	91.2 (prod), 154.1 (use)	/	Hydro recycling cuts GWP by ~52%; future mix biggest reducer
Kallitsis et al., 2022 [64]	LIBs (NMC)	Full pack	Cradle to gate + EoL	ReCiPe	~142;~98 (pyro);~91(hydro)	/	Hydro > pyro; Al, Cu, Ni, Co recovery drives benefits

Benveniste et al., 2022 [65]	LIBs (NMC)	1 kWh	Cradle to grave	CML 2011, ReCiPe 2008	394	/	Li-S has significantly lower GWP and resource use; requires industrial scaling
Porzio et al., 2022 [66]	LIBs (NMC+LMO blend)	1 kWh	Cradle to gate	Material mass % comparison	Not applicable	/	Review cathode mix (NMC vs LMO) affects sustainability and recyclability trade-offs
Chordia et al., 2022 [67]	LIBs (NMC)	1 kWh	Cradle to gate	ReCiPe Midpoint	109 (small) – 188 (giga)	/	small-scale pouch cell and giga-scale cylindrical cell production
Erakca et al., 2023 [68]	LIBs Lab-scale (NMC)	1 battery cell	Cradle to gate	OpenLCA 1.10	High (lab-scale)	/	Hotspots review: dry room & coating are key hotspots
Marashli et al., 2024 [69]	LIBs (Li-NMC + PV)	1 kWh	Cradle to grave	OpenLCA V1.11.0	189.36	Payback 5.7–17.5 yrs	Production = 76.9% GWP; recycling = 2.3%; highly location sensitive
Accardo et al., 2025 [71]	NMC 811	1 kWh battery capacity	Cradle to grave	EF 3.0	77.2 – 80.7	€77.7 – €79.4	The production phase has the highest GHG emissions due to the raw material extraction

Table 4 - Comparative Review of Lithium-based Battery Technologies

Notes to Impact categories:

- GWP is a metric that quantifies the relative impact of greenhouse gases on climate change over a specific time horizon, typically 100 years. It expresses the warming effect of a gas compared to carbon dioxide (CO₂), which has a reference value of 1.
- OpenLCA is an open-source software for LCA, used to model and analyze the environmental impacts of products, processes, or services.
- ReCiPe is LCIA method used to translate environmental emissions and resource use into potential impacts on human health, ecosystems, and resource availability. It provides both midpoint indicators (e.g. climate change, ozone depletion) and endpoint (damage) categories, enabling detailed and aggregated interpretation of LCA results.
- CED is a life cycle assessment indicator that measures the total amount of primary energy required throughout the life cycle of a product, process, or service. It includes both renewable and non-renewable energy sources, providing insight into overall energy intensity and resource use.
- Eco-indicator 99: Eco-indicator 99 is a LCIA method that evaluates the environmental impact of products and processes by aggregating emissions and resource extractions into damage categories: human health, ecosystem quality, and resource depletion. It uses endpoint indicators, allowing for a single score result to support decision-making and product comparisons.

- EF (Environmental Footprint): is a life cycle impact assessment method developed by the European Commission to evaluate the environmental performance of products, organizations, and sectors across their entire life cycle. It focuses on midpoint indicators (e.g. climate change, water use, resource depletion) and aims to harmonize LCA studies within the EU by providing a standardized and scientifically robust framework. EF is discussed later for the data analysis of GRAPHERGIA project.
- TRACI (Tool for the Reduction and Assessment of Chemical and Other Environmental Impacts): is an impact assessment method developed by the U.S. EPA and implemented in SimaPro. It provides midpoint impact results across categories such as climate change, acidification, eutrophication, human health, and resource depletion, making it particularly suitable for LCA studies in the North American context.

Functional Units and System Boundaries

Most studies adopt 1 kWh of battery capacity as the FU, which supports comparability across different battery chemistries and use cases (e.g., [57] [71]). However, alternative FU such as per battery pack [60] [54], per Wh [56]. These boundary choices strongly influence the scope, accuracy, and comparability of environmental performance results.

Life Cycle Impact Categories and Assessment Methods

Global Warming Potential and Emission Hotspots

Reported GWP values vary widely, ranging from 12.7 kg CO₂eq/kWh ([54], limited to assembly) to over 350 kg CO₂eq/kWh [55], with typical ranges for NMC and LFP chemistries lying between 75–200 kg CO₂eq/kWh (e.g., [71][57]).

Variability stems from differences in:

- Manufacturing energy demand
- Geographic electricity mix
- LCIA methods and data assumptions
- Material sourcing and logistics

Environmental hotspots are predominantly found in the battery production phase, particularly in the extraction and refinement of critical metals (e.g., cobalt, nickel), and energy-intensive processes such as electrode drying and coating.

Chemistry-Specific Trade-Offs

Battery chemistry significantly influences environmental impact:

- NMC batteries tend to have higher GWP due to cobalt and nickel content.

- Advanced materials like silicon nanowires (SiNW) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) lead to elevated GWP due to energy-intensive synthesis, with single-wall CNTs requiring up to 3 GWh/kg of embodied energy unless renewables are used [72].
- Cathode composition (e.g., NMC vs. LMO) also influences recyclability and total environmental impact [66].
- Recycling Benefits and EoL considerations.

Recycling and circularity offer substantial Global Warming Potential reductions

- Chen et al. (2022) [63] demonstrate that coupling recycling with low-carbon energy grids (e.g., Sweden, France) can reduce GWP by over 50%.
- Marashli et al. (2024) [69] highlight that the use-phase geography alone can affect energy payback times by up to 25%.

Despite these benefits, recycling effectiveness depends on technology (hydro vs pyro) and material purity, while not all battery designs are optimized for disassembly and resource recovery.

Life Cycle Costs and Eco-Costs

Few studies include economic impact analysis, and even fewer fully integrate it into the LCA framework:

- Accardo et al. (2025) [71] report €77.7–€79.4 per kWh for NMC811 batteries.
- Paul et al. (2024) [70] and Sadhukhan et al. (2021) [62] exemplify LCSA by combining LCA, LCC, and S-LCA perspectives.

However, such economic-environmental coupling remains limited across the literature.

Emerging Trends and Sector-Specific Insights

Recent studies emphasize:

- Expansion of LCSA frameworks that include social dimensions and multi-criteria indicators.
- Sector-specific applications (e.g. automotive, stationary storage), which present unique trade-offs based on duty cycles, usage profiles, and infrastructure contexts.
- Increased focus on recyclable and low-impact materials aligned with EU taxonomy and circular economy targets.

4 GRAPHERGIA data analysis

4.1 Life Cycle Assessment of Demonstrator #1: data analysis for smart textiles

Within the GRAPHERGIA project, Adamant Composites (ADA) is responsible for the design, fabrication and integration of graphene-enabled smart textiles for energy harvesting and storage, related to **Demonstrator #1**. The company develops textile-based demonstrators that combine advanced nanomaterials with flexible and wearable architectures, enabling self-charging functionalities and powering of low-consumption electronic devices. ADA also contributes to the optimization of manufacturing processes, ensuring scalability and industrial relevance, while supporting testing and validation activities to demonstrate the practical applicability of the developed solutions in real-life scenarios. ADA provided data supporting the production and technological development of LrGO-treated fabrics, composed by: (a) GO-treated fabrics produced using spraying technique and (b) GO-coated fabrics irradiation followed for the in-situ production of rGO using laser. The following image, **Figure 5**, provides an overview of the product's manufacturing process.

Figure 5 - Process production of GO-treated fabrics & rGO-treated fabrics

Preliminary LCA study

The FU selected for this study is 1 kg of rGO-treated textile. The system boundaries are defined as “cradle to gate”, covering all stages from raw material acquisition to the finished product ready for distribution (Packaging & Storage). The detailed LCI of the process has been compiled and is presented in **Table 6**. The graphene input was derived from the study by Bahmei et al. (2025) [82], used as a reference for the preliminary assessment. This paper compares the environmental

impact of producing graphene from biomass waste with that of the conventional Hummers' method. The [82] provides an inventory of materials required to produce 1 kg of dried hydrazine-reduced graphene oxide (h-rGO), based on the work of Serrano-Luján et al. (2019) [83].

The SimaPro method chosen was the EF3.1 Method, using the EF 3.1 normalization and weighting set (**Table 5** and **Table 6**). This is a version of the methodology developed by the European Commission to assess the environmental impacts of products, organizations, and sectors across their entire life cycle. Its primary aim is to harmonize LCA practices and ensure comparability of results at the European level. The 'adapted' designation refers to a modified implementation of the official EF3.1 Method, tailored for compatibility with professional LCA software tools, such as SimaPro. This version retains the scientific foundations and core principles of the EF3.1 standard, while incorporating practical adjustments, such as revised substance lists and unit conversions, to align with the structure of widely used LCA databases [77][78][79][80]. These adaptations ensure consistency and usability when applying the methodology in real-world assessments and allow for meaningful comparison with existing literature.

Impact Category (Abbreviations)	Unit	Impact Assessment Description
Acidification (AP)	mol H ⁺ eq	Emissions of acidifying substances (SO _x , NO _x , NH ₃) causing acidification of soils and water, with potential ecosystem damage.
Climate Change (CC)	kg CO ₂ eq	Contribution of greenhouse gases to changes in global air temperature and related climate effects over 100 years (GWP100).
Particulate matter formation (PM)	disease incidence (inc.)	Human health impacts from emissions of particulate matter (PM) and its precursors (NO _x , SO _x , NH ₃).
Fossil resource use (RU-foss)	MJ	Consumption of non-renewable fossil fuels, accounting for energy content.
Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEx)	CTUe	Potential toxic effects of substances on freshwater ecosystems, considering fate, exposure, and effect factors.
Freshwater eutrophication (FE)	kg P eq	Nutrient enrichment in freshwater ecosystems, leading to algal growth, oxygen depletion, and possible fish mortality.
Human carcinogenic toxicity (HTC)	CTUh	Adverse human health effects from exposure to carcinogenic substances via inhalation, ingestion, or dermal contact.
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HTNC)	CTUh	Adverse human health effects from non-carcinogenic substances via inhalation, ingestion, or dermal contact.
Ionizing radiation (IR)	kBq U-235 eq	Human health effects from exposure to ionizing radiation.
Land use (LU)	Pt	Land occupation and transformation measured as area-time, considering changes between land types.
Marine eutrophication (EM)	kg N eq	Nutrient enrichment in marine ecosystems, causing algal growth, oxygen depletion, and potential marine life mortality.

Ozone depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	Emissions of ozone-depleting substances (e.g., CFCs, HCFCs, halons) causing stratospheric ozone layer depletion.
Photochemical ozone formation (POF)	kg NMVOC eq	Ground-level ozone formation from NMVOCs and NO _x under sunlight, affecting human health, vegetation, and materials.
Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-mm)	kg Sb eq	Depletion of mineral and metal resources due to extraction and consumption, expressed in antimony (Sb) equivalents.
Terrestrial eutrophication (TE)	mol N eq	Nutrient enrichment (mainly N) in terrestrial ecosystems, leading to soil nutrient imbalance, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem degradation.
Water use (WU)	m ³ depriv.	Consumption of freshwater resources considering local water scarcity and availability impacts.

Table 5 - Impact Category Definitions for Environmental Footprint 3.1 (Adapted) V1.01

FU 1 kg rGO treated textile	Process Input	Material	Value	Unit	SimaPro Process
Raw Materials	Precursor	Water	2.42	kg	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Alloc Def, U
		Graphene Oxide	0.01	kg	Graphene_NTT Elaboration based on [82]
	Substrate	Polyester	0.48	kg	Fibre, polyester {GLO} market for fibre, polyester Cut-off, U
	Protective Film	Silicone	0.49	kg	Silicone product {RER} production Alloc Def, U
Consumables	Cleaning of the lines, lab, & other surfaces and lab materials through the process	Paper	0.25	kg	Tissue paper {RER} production Alloc Def, U
		Isopropyl alcohol	0.39	kg	Isopropyl acetate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Acetone	0.40	kg	Acetone, liquid {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		DI Water	2	kg	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Alloc Def, U
		Polypropylene	0.01	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
PPE	PPE used during process	NBR - nitrile butadiene rubber	0.04	kg	Synthetic rubber {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U

		Polypropylene	0.12	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Polypropylene	0.11	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
Spraying Process - Preparation	Preparation of water based GO - mixing	Electricity	0.5	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	R2R Pilot Line - Spraying Process	Electricity	1.84	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
Laser Process	R2R Pilot Line - Laser Process	Electricity	19.72	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
Transportation	Transport of GO from Spain to Greece	Transport - Aircraft	0.03	tkm	Transport, freight, aircraft {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Transport - Truck	0.002	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Transport of Fabrics from Germany to Greece	Transport - Truck	1.15	tkm	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
Packaging & Storage	Packaging & Storage	Plastic (PE)	0.63	kg	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Cardboard	1	kg	Corrugated board box {GLO} market for corrugated board box Alloc Def, U
Output					
Wastes	Protective Gloves	Waste	0.04	kg	Waste rubber, unspecified {CH} market for waste rubber, unspecified Cut-off, U
	Cleaning Paper	Waste	0.25	kg	Waste graphical paper {Europe without Switzerland} market group for waste graphical paper Cut-off, U
	IPA	Waste	0.001	m ³	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U
	Acetone	Waste	0.001	m ³	
	Protective film-roll for the treated fabric	Waste	0.49	kg	Waste plastic, mixture {Europe without Switzerland} market group for waste plastic, mixture Cut-off, U

Table 6 - LCI of 1 kg rGO treated textile

4.1.1 Preliminary LCA Results for Demonstrator #1

This section presents the main results of the preliminary LCA carried out on the rGO-treated textile, based on data modeling and analysis performed using SimaPro v10.2. The aim is to identify the most impactful processes and input flows across selected environmental indicators, in line with the EF3.1 Method. The results are organized to support both a global interpretation and a more detailed analysis, as described below.

Tables 7 and 8 display the damage categories, along with their corresponding units, as defined by the EF3.1 Method, for each input modeled in the system. To facilitate a clearer and more concise interpretation, the results have been aggregated by process. A detailed breakdown of all individual SimaPro processes is provided in the Appendix.

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Raw Materials	Consumables	PPE	Transport	Packaging & Storage	Spraying Process-Preparation	Laser Process	Waste Man.
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	1.78E+00	1.60E+00	1.67E-02	2.55E-03	7.45E-04	5.08E-03	1.68E-02	1.41E-01	3.16E-04
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	9.30E+01	6.47E+01	2.72E+00	6.03E-01	1.98E-01	9.10E-01	2.43E+00	2.05E+01	9.41E-01
Fex (CTUe)	4.33E+04	4.32E+04	9.75E+00	7.38E-01	7.87E-01	2.25E+00	1.11E+01	9.38E+01	3.33E+00
PM (disease inc.)	5.03E-06	4.25E-06	1.56E-07	3.04E-08	1.92E-08	5.19E-08	5.49E-08	4.63E-07	2.27E-09
ME (kg N eq)	6.63E-01	6.47E-01	2.21E-03	4.44E-04	2.37E-04	1.09E-03	1.21E-03	1.02E-02	2.36E-04
Fe (kg P eq)	2.08E-02	1.49E-02	1.01E-04	1.30E-05	2.28E-07	2.22E-05	6.12E-04	5.15E-03	1.91E-06
TE (mol N eq)	7.12E+00	6.96E+00	2.36E-02	4.79E-03	2.60E-03	9.17E-03	1.27E-02	1.07E-01	1.51E-03
HTC (CTUh)	1.05E-06	1.05E-06	4.48E-10	5.09E-11	2.92E-11	2.30E-10	3.59E-10	3.03E-09	2.56E-10
HTNC (CTUh)	1.16E-06	9.65E-07	1.37E-08	9.94E-10	1.90E-09	4.64E-09	1.81E-08	1.53E-07	3.96E-09
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	2.81E+00	1.49E+00	8.04E-01	1.17E-02	1.26E-02	2.37E-02	4.95E-02	4.17E-01	1.42E-04
LU (Pt)	7.28E+01	3.95E+01	7.70E+00	2.96E-01	1.46E-02	1.37E+01	1.20E+00	1.01E+01	2.15E-01
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	9.28E-06	9.01E-06	1.87E-08	9.33E-10	8.31E-11	4.76E-09	2.56E-08	2.16E-07	4.69E-10
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.74E+00	1.67E+00	1.54E-02	2.35E-03	7.23E-04	3.48E-03	4.21E-03	3.55E-02	4.84E-04
RU-fos (MJ)	1.41E+03	9.61E+02	7.41E+01	1.98E+01	2.84E+00	2.12E+01	3.51E+01	2.96E+02	2.85E-01

RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	3.12E-05	2.42E-05	5.80E-07	3.08E-06	6.83E-10	1.20E-06	2.33E-07	1.96E-06	1.10E-08
WU (m ³ depriv.)	2.49E+01	1.89E+01	3.25E+00	2.22E-01	1.24E-02	4.01E-01	2.31E-01	1.94E+00	-5.42E-02

Table 7 - Results of LCA (Environmental Footprint 3.1 (adapted) V1.01 / EF 3.1 normalization and weighting set)

Damage Category (Unit)	Raw Materials	Consumables	PPE	Transport	Packaging & Storage	Spraying Process- Preparation	Laser Proces	Waste Management
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	89.70%	0.94%	0.14%	0.04%	0.29%	0.94%	7.94%	0.02%
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	69.58%	2.92%	0.65%	0.21%	0.98%	2.61%	22.04%	1.01%
Fex (CTUe)	99.72%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%	0.22%	0.01%
PM (disease inc.)	84.55%	3.09%	0.60%	0.38%	1.03%	1.09%	9.20%	0.05%
ME (kg N eq)	97.64%	0.33%	0.07%	0.04%	0.16%	0.18%	1.54%	0.04%
Fe (kg P eq)	71.63%	0.48%	0.06%	0.00%	0.11%	2.94%	24.77%	0.01%
TE (mol N eq)	97.74%	0.33%	0.07%	0.04%	0.13%	0.18%	1.50%	0.02%
HTC (CTUh)	99.58%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.03%	0.29%	0.02%
HTNC (CTUh)	83.12%	1.18%	0.09%	0.16%	0.40%	1.56%	13.15%	0.34%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	53.10%	28.58%	0.42%	0.45%	0.84%	1.76%	14.84%	0.01%
LU (Pt)	54.34%	10.58%	0.41%	0.02%	18.78%	1.65%	13.93%	0.30%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	97.13%	0.20%	0.01%	0.00%	0.05%	0.28%	2.33%	0.01%
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	96.42%	0.89%	0.14%	0.04%	0.20%	0.24%	2.04%	0.03%
RU-fos (MJ)	68.16%	5.26%	1.40%	0.20%	1.50%	2.49%	20.97%	0.02%
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	77.39%	1.86%	9.86%	0.00%	3.83%	0.74%	6.28%	0.04%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	75.49%	13.03%	0.89%	0.05%	1.61%	0.93%	7.80%	-0.22%

Table 8 - Main Input Distribution in percentage (%)

Figure 5 - Percentage Categories Process (%)

As shown in **Table 7 and Table 8**, Raw Materials phase is the main contributor to the overall environmental impact, accounting on average for 82.20% of total impacts.

This contribution ranges from a maximum of 99% for the Ecotoxicity Freshwater (FEx) and Human Toxicity (HTC) categories, followed by Terrestrial Eutrophication (TE) and Ozone Depletion (OD) (97%), to a minimum of 53% for Ionising Radiation (IR).

The second largest contributor is the Laser Process phase, accounting for an average of approximately 9.3% of the total impacts, with the highest contribution observed in the Climate Change (CC) category (22.04%). Consumables contribute 4.36%, while the remaining 4.11% is associated with Transport, Packaging, and Waste management processes.

Figure 7 presents a histogram that visually highlights the percentage contribution of each process, further emphasizing the significantly higher impact of Raw Materials compared to the others.

A focus on CC (also called CF) shows that 69.58% of the impact is attributable to Raw Materials (65.59% to the input h-rGO), 22.4% to Laser Process and the remaining 8.39% to Transport, Packaging, Spraying process, and Waste management (**Figure 8**).

Figure 6 - CF for Damage Category

Preliminary analysis indicates that the rGO represents the most impactful input within the system, as assessed using the Environmental Footprint 3.1 method, with a total CF amounts to 93 kg CO₂eq.

The Laser Process also has a significant environmental impact, ranking second with a CF of 20.5 kg CO₂eq. This is primarily due to the high contribution of electricity consumption, as modeled using the SimaPro database. Given its considerable influence on the overall environmental performance, this process requires further analysis and targeted optimization. Priority should be given to strategies that optimize raw material selection, improve and reduce energy efficiency in order to mitigate the impact of this production steps.

4.1.2 Preliminary Eco-Cost Results for Demonstrator#1

The Eco-Cost assessment carried out within the GRAPHERGIA project has delivered a monetized evaluation of the environmental impacts linked to the life cycles of the selected products. By integrating LCI data with external cost factors across multiple impact categories (such as climate change, human and eco-toxicity, land use, and resource depletion), the analysis enables a consistent and transparent comparison of environmental performance among the different technological solutions investigated.

Notes for Tables 9 & 13:

- “– €” = Values are not available due to the absence of monetary conversion factors for the respective category in the literature.
- “<E-03 €” = Values fall below the threshold of E-03 and are omitted in monetary form both for space considerations and because of their negligible significance.
- “0.00 €” = Values reported as zero correspond to originally negative results. These are treated as zero since the absence of environmental impact cannot be considered a positive contribution to environmental quality, but rather a “non-impact” that does not exacerbate the ecological conditions associated with the production process under analysis.

The Eco-Cost analysis (**Table 9**) indicates a total of 34.94 € and that the Raw Materials is the most environmentally burdensome stage (28.03 €), followed by Laser Process (4.61 €). The combined Eco-Cost of Consumables, personal protective equipment (PPE), Transport, Packaging & Storage, and Waste management amounts to 2 € of environmental cost.

These results highlight the environmental impact of the Raw Materials (in particular rGO with 26.9 € eco-cost) relative to other stages in the production chain (visual highlight in **Figure 9**).

Impact Category (Unit)	Raw Materials	Consumables	PPE	Transport	Packaging & Storage	Spraying Process-Preparation	Laser Process	Waste Management
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	0.61 €	0.01 €	0.001 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	0.01 €	0.05 €	<E-03 €
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	5.97 €	0.25 €	0.06 €	0.02 €	0.08 €	0.22 €	1.89 €	0.09 €
Fex (CTUe)	1.85 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.004 €	<E-03 €
PM (disease inc.)	3.73 €	0.14 €	0.03 €	0.02 €	0.05 €	0.05 €	0.41 €	0.002 €
ME (kg N eq)	3.52 €	0.01 €	0.002 €	0.001 €	0.01 €	0.01 €	0.06 €	0.001 €
Fe (kg P eq)	0.03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.001 €	0.01 €	<E-03 €
TE (mol N eq)	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
HTC (CTUh)	1.00 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.003 €	<E-03 €
HTNC (CTUh)	0.17 €	0.002 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.003 €	0.03 €	<E-03 €
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	0.17 €	0.09 €	0.001 €	0.001 €	0.003 €	0.01 €	0.05 €	<E-03 €
LU (Pt)	0.04 €	0.01 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.01 €	0.001 €	0.01 €	<E-03 €
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €

POF (kg NMVOC eq)	4.34 €	0.04 €	0.01 €	0.002 €	0.01 €	0.01 €	0.09 €	0.001 €
RU-fos (MJ)	6.47 €	0.50 €	0.13 €	0.02 €	0.14 €	0.24 €	1.99 €	0.002 €
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
WU (m ³ depriv.)	0.11 €	0.02 €	0.001 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	0.001 €	0.01 €	0.00 €
Total	28.03 €	1.07 €	0.23 €	0.06 €	0.31 €	0.55 €	4.61 €	0.09 €

Table 9 - Eco-Cost results for rGO treated textile

Figure 7 - Overall Eco-Cost for rGO treated textile

The current body of literature concerning LCA studies on smart textiles is scarce. The few available studies, as discussed in the previous section, employ methodologies, FU, and system boundaries that differ significantly from those defined within the GRAPHERGIA Project.

For the CF, the current results from GRAPHERGIA appear to be less impactful compared to those reported by Dulal et al. (2024) [45] and van der Velden et al. (2015) [46] form a preliminary evaluation.

Overall, although still preliminary, these findings are promising. They demonstrate that the use of graphene and the specific technologies developed within GRAPHERGIA are less impactful than those documented in the existing literature, thus offering a more sustainable pathway for the development of advanced smart textiles.

Consequently, meaningful comparisons cannot be directly established. In this context, the GRAPHERGIA project plays a crucial role, as it will generate new knowledge and fill critical gaps required for the systematic application of graphene-based technologies in the textile sector and provide the scientific foundation needed to unlock the sustainable application of graphene technology in textiles.

It is important to note that the preliminary LCA analysis (as Eco-cost) presented in this report refers only to a specific component of the technology foreseen for Demonstrator #1, the development of rGO-treated fabrics. This component represents an initial stage of assessment and does not yet encompass the full range of materials, processes, and applications envisaged within the demonstrator.

Demonstrator #1 is designed to integrate this innovative textile technology into a variety of end-use scenarios, including smart textiles (e.g., healthcare and sports applications) (CS1), as well as upholstery e-textiles (CS2). Each of these use cases will involve distinct material inputs, functional requirements, and manufacturing processes, which will have a significant influence on the overall environmental and economic performance.

Consequently, a complete and more accurate LCA will be conducted once detailed data on all relevant components, processes, and use cases become available. This full-system analysis will provide a more reliable basis for evaluating environmental impacts and will enable a more robust comparison with existing products and systems found in scientific literature.

Moreover, this extended assessment will be essential to guide decision-making in terms of eco-design, by identifying key environmental hotspots and supporting the selection of low-impact materials, production methods, and EoL strategies. It will also ensure that the developed technologies are aligned with the principles of the circular economy and meet current and forthcoming European regulatory requirements, such as those related to sustainability, recyclability, and CF reduction.

Ultimately, this approach supports not only the environmental performance optimization of the demonstrator, but also its industrial scalability and market readiness within the framework of European green innovation policies.

4.2 Life Cycle Assessment of Demonstrator #3: data analysis LIBs for space applications

Within the GRAPHERGIA project, Pleione Energy S.A. (PLE) will focus its activities on the development and optimization of LIBs. PLE will work on integrating graphene-based materials into battery electrodes to enhance their electrochemical performance, durability, and safety. The company will conduct testing and validation of advanced cell prototypes, ensuring that the new materials meet industrial standards and can be scaled up for commercial applications. The technology for LIBs graphene-anode will be provided by The Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH). PLE developed a Graphene-based LIB pouch cell (400 mAh). **Figure 8** illustrates the production process of LIBs pouch cells by PLE.

Figure 8 - PLE process production of LIB pouch cell

Preliminary LCA study

The FU selected for this study is a graphene-based LIB pouch cell (400 mAh) produced by PLE. The system boundaries are defined as “cradle to gate”, encompassing all stages involved in the production and assembly of the LIB pouch cell. The applied methodology is described in detail in Section 2.2, 'Methodology for Life Cycle Assessment'. The SimaPro method chosen was EF3.1 Method. The detailed LCI of the process has been compiled and is presented in **Table 10**.

Process values, especially those related to electricity, were modified to enhance the robustness and reliability of the results, with Raw Materials being the sole exception. The updated parameters were calculated applying the conversion factor reported by [81]. It should be stressed that these findings represent a preliminary assessment and require further refinement. The adjustment of PLE-provided data was necessary, since some input values were identified as overestimated in both environmental and economic dimensions, thereby introducing potential distortions into the overall analysis.

FU Graphene-based LIB pouch cell (400 mAh)	Process Input	Material	Value	Unit	SimaPro Process
Raw materials	Graphene for Anode slurry	Commercial graphene	/	kg	<i>Missing Data (It will be added as the project progresses).</i>
	Conductive Additive for Anode slurry	Carbon black	3.00E-03	kg	Carbon black {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Binder for Anode	Rubber binder	5.00E-03	kg	Synthetic rubber {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Surfactant	3.00E-04	kg	Alkylbenzene sulfonate, linear, petrochemical {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Slurry solvent	Deionized water	9.97E-02	kg	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Alloc Def, U
	Substrate of Anode	Copper foil	1.14E-02	kg	Copper, cathode {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Separator	Polymer Separator	2.40E-03	kg	Packaging film, low density polyethylene {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Cathode	Commercial NCA	1.50E-02	kg	Cathode, NCA, for Li-ion battery {RoW} market for cathode, NCA, for Li-ion battery Cut-off, U
	Pouch cell casing	Pouch foil laminated aluminum film	1.25E-02	kg	Aluminium, primary, ingot {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
					Sheet rolling, aluminium {RoW} processing Alloc Def, U
	Electrolyte	LiPF ₆	1.95E-02	kg	Lithium hexafluorophosphate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Terminal of Anode	Nickel tab	3.00E-04	kg	Nickel, 99.5%, at plant/GLO U
	Terminal of Cathode	Aluminum tab	1.00E-04	kg	Aluminium, primary, ingot {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
Consumables	Cleaning of working surfaces	Cleaning paper	7.44E-06	kg	Tissue paper {RER} production Alloc Def, U

	coating process and electrode preparation	Isopropyl Alcohol	2.92E-05	kg	Isopropyl acetate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Acetone	2.94E-05	kg	Acetone, liquid {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Deionized water	3.72E-05	kg	Tap water {Europe without Switzerland} market for Alloc Def, U
		Filter paper	7.44E-06	kg	Tissue paper {RER} production Alloc Def, U
Slurry preparation	Nanomaterials handling	Glove box 1	6.70E-05	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Weight measurement of the materials	Scale	2.23E-06	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Mixing and Evaporation of Slurry	Fume hood	1.49E-03	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Sonication of graphene nanoplatelets	Magnetic Stirrer and heater	2.07E-03	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
		Ultrasonic probe	1.49E-04	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Electrode drying	Oven	5.14E-03	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
Cell Assembly	Terminal tab welding	Ultrasonic welder	7.44E-06	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Presealing of the cell	Soldering Iron	1.86E-06	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Electrodes conditioning and full assembly drying	Vacuum pump	8.93E-06	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
		Vacuum oven	2.60E-03	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Drying of the environment	AC	4.47E-02	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Anode Electrode calendaring	Rolling machine	8.93E-04	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing	Purging	Vacuum pump	1.38E-04	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Purifying filling environment	Nitrogen	9.30E-06	kg	Nitrogen, liquid {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Electrolyte filling	Syringe	1.17E-05	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Sealing of cell	Vacuum sealer	4.47E-04	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
Degassing	Purging	Vacuum pump	1.38E-04	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U

	Purifying filling environment	Nitrogen	9.30E-06	kg	Nitrogen, liquid {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Electrolyte addition if it needed	Syringe	1.17E-05	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
	Sealing of cell	Vacuum sealer	4.47E-04	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
Cells characterization	Charge/ Discharge	Battery tester MTI Corporation BST8-5A-CST	3.13E-03	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy	Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat / galvanostat	1.40E-05	kWh	Electricity, medium voltage {GR} market for Alloc Def, U
PPE	Protective equipment used during the process	Nitrile butadiene rubber protective gloves	1.36E-04	kg	Synthetic rubber {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
		Protective mask	2.98E-04	kg	Polypropylene, granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Def, U
Output					
Wastes	Cleaning paper	Waste	1.00E-02	kg	Waste graphical paper {Europe without Switzerland} market group for waste graphical paper Cut-off, U
	Isopropyl Alcohol	Waste	3.93E-05	m ³	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U
	Acetone	Waste	3.95E-05	m ³	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U
	Deionized water	Waste	5.00E-05	kg	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U
	Filter paper	Waste	1.00E-02	kg	Waste graphical paper {Europe without Switzerland} market group for waste graphical paper Cut-off, U

Table 10 - Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of LIB pouch cell

4.2.1 Preliminary LCA Results for Demonstrator #3

The preliminary LCA of the PLE LIB was performed considering a single 400 mAh pouch cell as the functional FU. This methodological choice diverges from most studies in literature, which typically adopt 1 kWh or other energy-based functional units. As a result, direct comparisons with published data cannot be established; however, meaningful trends can still be identified. For the final study (M42), the assessments may be reformulated based on a different FU focusing on the amount of energy, for example in kWh.

The results clearly indicate that Raw material extraction and processing are the dominant contributors, accounting for more than 90% (average 97.73%) of the total impact across all categories. The overall CF is estimated at 236 kg CO₂eq, which appears relatively high when considering the modest capacity and weight of the battery, but nonetheless remains within the range reported in the literature. These findings are consistent with previous works highlighting the crucial role of raw materials in shaping the environmental profile of LIBs. The Raw Material inputs with the highest impact are lithium hexafluorophosphate (40.20%), the NCA Li-ion battery cathode (25.92%), and aluminum (19.65%) for the CC category, with a similar trend observed across the other impact categories (for further details, reference is made to the Appendix).

In addition to Raw Materials, the subsequent most relevant contributors are cell assembly and electricity consumption, which together account for approximately 2% (average 1.73%) of the total impacts. Although secondary compared to Raw Materials, these phases may still play a non-negligible role when considering process optimization or scale-up scenarios. These findings are consistent with the GWP hotspots identified in literature studies [62][70][71].

It is important to note that the results may be partially affected by the recalibration of several input parameters, which were initially overestimated (as also observed in the LCC data provided). This limitation underlines the need for further refinement of the life cycle inventory and the adoption of harmonized methodological assumptions. Future work should therefore focus on improving data quality, expanding system boundaries, and exploring alternative FU to enable comparability with the broader body of literature. Such efforts are essential to enhance the robustness of the assessment and to provide a more comprehensive and reliable evaluation of the sustainability of PLE LIB technologies. All the results are presented in **Tables 11 and 12** and in **Figure 9** (and in Appendix).

Abbreviations: In the tables, cells characterization is abbreviated as "cells charact"; Consumables is abbreviated as "Consum."

Damage Category	Total	Raw Materials	Consum.	Slurry Preparation	Coating and drying process	Cell Assembly	Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing	Degassing	Cells charact.	PPE	Waste
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	3.36E+00	2.29E-04	5.08E-03	6.92E-03	6.49E-02	8.08E-04	8.08E-04	4.23E-03	8.86E-04	1.23E-03
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	2.22E+02	3.73E-02	7.37E-01	1.00E+00	9.40E+00	1.19E-01	1.19E-01	6.13E-01	1.91E-01	2.23E+00
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	1.46E+03	1.33E-01	3.37E+00	4.59E+00	4.31E+01	5.26E-01	5.26E-01	2.81E+00	4.11E-01	1.78E+01

PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	2.28E-05	2.13E-09	1.66E-08	2.26E-08	2.12E-07	2.79E-09	2.79E-09	1.39E-08	1.08E-08	1.03E-08
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	3.12E-01	3.02E-05	3.68E-04	5.00E-04	4.69E-03	6.07E-05	6.07E-05	3.06E-04	1.42E-04	1.91E-03
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	8.16E-02	1.38E-06	1.85E-04	2.52E-04	2.37E-03	2.89E-05	2.89E-05	1.54E-04	4.28E-06	4.04E-05
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	3.19E+00	3.24E-04	3.85E-03	5.23E-03	4.91E-02	6.36E-04	6.36E-04	3.20E-03	1.55E-03	5.37E-03
HTC (CTUh)	2.13E-07	2.11E-07	5.91E-12	1.09E-10	1.48E-10	1.39E-09	1.73E-11	1.73E-11	9.06E-11	1.91E-11	3.42E-10
HTNC (CTUh)	1.11E-05	1.09E-05	1.80E-10	5.49E-09	7.47E-09	7.01E-08	8.59E-10	8.59E-10	4.57E-09	3.97E-10	1.73E-08
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	1.77E+01	9.22E-03	1.50E-02	2.04E-02	1.91E-01	2.43E-03	2.43E-03	1.25E-02	7.09E-03	8.84E-04
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	5.42E+02	9.34E-02	3.64E-01	4.96E-01	4.65E+00	5.84E-02	5.84E-02	3.03E-01	1.86E-01	1.02E+00
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	1.19E-05	2.50E-10	7.77E-09	1.06E-08	9.91E-08	1.23E-09	1.23E-09	6.46E-09	5.40E-10	1.86E-09
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.02E+00	9.94E-01	2.13E-04	1.28E-03	1.74E-03	1.63E-02	2.17E-04	2.17E-04	1.06E-03	7.40E-04	2.27E-03
RU-fos (MJ)	3.45E+03	3.27E+03	9.89E-01	1.06E+01	1.45E+01	1.36E+02	1.82E+00	1.82E+00	8.85E+00	6.07E+00	1.24E+00
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	1.66E-02	7.79E-09	7.05E-08	9.59E-08	8.99E-07	1.11E-08	1.11E-08	5.86E-08	1.96E-06	4.73E-08
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	1.41E+03	4.03E-02	6.99E-02	9.51E-02	8.92E-01	2.70E-02	2.70E-02	5.82E-02	7.92E-02	-1.18E+00

Table 11 - Results of preliminary LCA with EF3.1 Method

Damage Category	Raw Materials	Consumption	Slurry Preparation	Coating and drying process	Cell Assembly	Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing	Degassing	Cells character.	PPE	Waste
AP (molH ⁺ eq)	97.53%	0.01%	0.15%	0.20%	2.09%	0.02%	0.02%	0.12%	0.03%	0.04%
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	93.89%	0.02%	0.31%	0.42%	4.40%	0.05%	0.05%	0.26%	0.08%	0.94%
FEx (CTUe)	95.21%	0.01%	0.22%	0.30%	3.12%	0.03%	0.03%	0.18%	0.03%	1.16%
PM (disease inc.)	98.72%	0.01%	0.07%	0.10%	1.02%	0.01%	0.01%	0.06%	0.05%	0.04%

ME (kg N eq)	97.48%	0.01%	0.11%	0.16%	1.62%	0.02%	0.02%	0.10%	0.04%	0.60%
FE (kg P eq)	96.39%	0.00%	0.22%	0.30%	3.09%	0.03%	0.03%	0.18%	0.01%	0.05%
TE (mol N eq)	97.85%	0.01%	0.12%	0.16%	1.67%	0.02%	0.02%	0.10%	0.05%	0.16%
HTC (CTUh)	99.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.07%	0.72%	0.01%	0.01%	0.04%	0.01%	0.16%
HTNC (CTUh)	99.03%	0.00%	0.05%	0.07%	0.70%	0.01%	0.01%	0.04%	0.00%	0.16%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	98.54%	0.05%	0.08%	0.11%	1.18%	0.01%	0.01%	0.07%	0.04%	0.00%
LU (Pt)	98.68%	0.02%	0.07%	0.09%	0.94%	0.01%	0.01%	0.06%	0.03%	0.19%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	98.92%	0.00%	0.06%	0.09%	0.92%	0.01%	0.01%	0.05%	0.00%	0.02%
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	97.64%	0.02%	0.13%	0.17%	1.77%	0.02%	0.02%	0.10%	0.07%	0.22%
RU-fos (MJ)	94.74%	0.03%	0.31%	0.42%	4.35%	0.05%	0.05%	0.26%	0.18%	0.04%
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	99.98%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	99.99%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	-0.08%

Table 12 - Main Input Distribution in percentage (%)

Figure 9 - CF Damage Category

4.2.2 Preliminary Eco-Cost Results for Demonstrator #3

Similarly, for the eco-cost assessment (**Table 13** and **Figure 10**), the most impactful phase is that of Raw materials, accounting for 81.05€ out of a total of 84.08€. The Cell Assembly phase represents the second-largest contribution, amounting to 2.11€. For a detailed interpretation of the table, reference is made to Section 4.1.2, "Eco-Cost Study Results for Demonstrator #1." The remaining contributions to the eco-cost are negligible.

Impact Category (Unit)	Raw Materials	Consum.	Slurry Preparation	Coating and drying process	Cell Assembly	Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing	Degassing	Cells charact.	PPE	Waste
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	1.29 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	0.003 €	0.02 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	20.50 €	0.003 €	0.07 €	0.09 €	0.86 €	0.01 €	0.01 €	0.06 €	0.02 €	0.21 €
Fex (CTUe)	0.06 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
PM (disease inc.)	19.98 €	0.002 €	0.01 €	0.02 €	0.19 €	0.002 €	0.002 €	0.01 €	0.01 €	0.01 €
ME (kg N eq)	1.70 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	0.003 €	0.03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.002 €	<E-03 €	0.01 €
Fe (kg P eq)	0.18 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.005 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
TE (mol N eq)	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €	- €
HTC (CTUh)	0.20 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.001 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
HTNC (CTUh)	1.96 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.001 €	0.01 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.003 €
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	2.07 €	0.001 €	0.002 €	0.002 €	0.02 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.001 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
LU (Pt)	0.59 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.005 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.001 €
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	2.57 €	<E-03 €	0.003 €	0.004 €	0.04 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.003	0.002 €	0.006 €
RU-fos (MJ)	22.02 €	0.007 €	0.07 €	0.10 €	0.91 €	0.01 €	0.01 €	0.06 €	0.04 €	0.008 €
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	0.03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €
WU	7.90 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	<E-03 €	0.00 €

(m ³ depriv.)										
Total	81.05 €	0.014 €	0.16 €	0.23 €	2.11 €	0.028 €	0.028 €	0.14 €	0.072 €	0.24 €

Table 13 - Eco-Cost results for LIB pouch cell

Figure 10 - Overall Eco-Cost for LIB pouch cell

Demonstrator #3 is designed for space applications (CubeSats). However, the data currently available only allow for a preliminary environmental assessment of the LIB pouch cells, limited to the LCA and Eco-Cost analyses. Although the scientific literature provides a considerable amount of data on lithium-ion batteries, most studies are focused on automotive and stationary applications and rely on technologies that partially differ from those developed within GRAPHERGIA. As a result, it is not yet possible to perform a fully representative benchmarking analysis specifically tailored to space-related applications; instead, only technology-level comparisons can be established at this stage.

For the final LCA, the integration of project-generated data with the currently missing parameters will enable a comprehensive sustainability evaluation of the final battery module. This will include a robust assessment of environmental, economic, and social impacts, ensuring methodological consistency with the project’s objectives and contributing to a more accurate and reliable sustainability profile of graphene-enabled LIB technologies for space applications.

5 Preliminary evaluation and conclusions

D6.1 presents the first integrated evaluation of the environmental and economic performance of selected graphene-based technologies developed within the GRAPHERGIA project. The analysis builds on the methodological framework defined in Tasks 6.1 and 6.2, combining Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Eco-Cost analysis and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) under a Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) perspective. The objective is to provide early insights into the sustainability profile of the demonstrators, identify critical hotspots, and support eco-design and process optimisation in subsequent stages of the project.

The assessments were performed for **Demonstrator #1** (self-charging textile for energy harvesting and storage) and **Demonstrator #3** (graphene-based lithium-ion battery module). These case studies were selected as sufficient process and material data were available to allow meaningful modelling. **Demonstrator #2** (self-powered wireless sensor) will be evaluated in future project phases once representative data become available, ensuring methodological consistency across all demonstrators.

The LCAs were conducted using SimaPro 10.2 with the Ecoinvent 3.11 database, applying a cradle-to-gate system boundary and ISO 14040/14044-compliant procedures. Where applicable, limited use-phase assumptions were explored qualitatively to assess potential contributions to the overall environmental performance, though no quantitative modelling of the use phase was included at this stage. Similarly, End-of-Life (EoL) considerations were excluded from the current analysis due to the early TRL of the demonstrators and lack of data on graphene-based component recycling or recovery. These aspects will be integrated in the final assessment foreseen at M42.

The results indicate that, for both assessed demonstrators, the material synthesis and processing stages remain the main contributors to the overall environmental impacts, primarily due to the energy requirements associated with graphene production and related material processing. However, for Demonstrator #1, the in situ deposition process developed by FORTH and ADAMANT represents a significant improvement in environmental performance. This process enables the direct growth of high-quality graphene layers onto flexible substrates using a water-based graphene oxide (GO) dispersion as the sole precursor, thereby eliminating the need for pre- or post-treatment steps involving harmful chemicals. Consequently, the textile demonstrator shows reduced chemical-related impacts compared to conventional coating or functionalisation routes. The most relevant impact categories across both demonstrators remain global warming

potential (GWP), cumulative energy demand, and resource depletion, but the adoption of cleaner synthesis routes indicates strong potential for further optimisation and footprint reduction.

In contrast, manufacturing and assembly processes contributed less to the total impacts, reflecting the limited scale and manual nature of laboratory production. However, these results are expected to evolve as industrial-scale processes are defined and modelled. Sensitivity analyses in the next reporting period will evaluate how alternative synthesis routes, renewable energy use, and recycling strategies may improve the environmental performance.

From an economic-environmental perspective, Eco-Cost analysis was applied to monetise environmental burdens and provide an initial indication of potential “hidden costs” of environmental damage. Results confirm the findings of the LCA, with the synthesis phase emerging as the main cost driver. The Eco-Cost outcomes also provide a basis for future comparison with LCC results, which will be developed once representative cost data are available. This approach will allow quantifying trade-offs between environmental impact reduction and economic feasibility, supporting decision-making for technology upscaling.

Although quantitative LCC analysis has not yet been performed, the methodological framework has been defined and harmonised with the LCA structure. Future LCC activities will include the evaluation of capital expenditures (CAPEX), operational costs (OPEX), and cost sensitivity to raw material prices, energy costs, and regulatory changes (e.g., carbon pricing). This will enable a robust assessment of the cost-effectiveness and market scalability of GRAPHERGIA innovations.

The preliminary assessment highlights several **key opportunities for improvement**:

- **Process optimisation**: substituting energy-intensive or hazardous reagents with greener alternatives and improving synthesis yields.
- **Material substitution**: exploring bio-based or recycled feedstocks for graphene and polymer matrices to enhance circularity.
- **Energy sourcing**: adopting renewable energy inputs for material synthesis and component processing.
- **Design optimisation**: reducing material demand through improved architecture and lightweight design.

Moreover, the eco-design strategy (Task 5.1) will be continuously informed by the LCA and Eco-Cost outcomes, ensuring that sustainability criteria are embedded in the technological development pathway. The iterative feedback between WP5 and WP6 will help minimise environmental burdens while maximising functionality and performance.

Benchmarking against comparable technologies (e.g., conventional batteries, smart textiles, aerospace sensors) demonstrates that GRAPHERGIA's graphene-based solutions have strong

potential for impact reduction, particularly in terms of material efficiency and energy recovery potential. However, their actual benefits will depend on future scale-up, material sourcing, and recyclability improvements.

Looking ahead, the next steps will focus on refining the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) as the demonstrators evolve, integrating updated datasets, and including EoL and use-phase modelling. The final sustainability assessment (M42) will deliver a comprehensive cradle-to-grave analysis, complemented by quantitative LCC and Social LCA (Task 6.3) results. This will provide a holistic picture of the environmental, economic, and social performance of GRAPHERGIA technologies and guide their transition towards industrial readiness and market viability.

In conclusion, Deliverable 6.1 establishes a solid methodological and analytical baseline for the sustainability evaluation of GRAPHERGIA technologies. Despite the current limitations in data availability, the results offer valuable early insights into environmental and economic hotspots, guiding eco-design decisions and future optimisation efforts. The integration of refined LCA, LCC, and S-LCA analyses in the final phase of the project will ensure a comprehensive understanding of the sustainability potential of graphene-based innovations, supporting their alignment with EU climate neutrality and circular economy goals.

PENDING FOR EC APPROVAL

6 References

- [1] Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC). (1993). A Conceptual Framework for Life Cycle Impact Assessment. SETAC-Europe, Brussels. Available at <https://www.setac.org/resource/conceptual-framework-for-life-cycle-impact-assessment.html>
- [2] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2006). ISO 14040: Environmental Management – Life Cycle Assessment – Principles and Framework. Geneva: ISO.
- [3] International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2006). ISO 14044: Environmental Management – Life Cycle Assessment – Requirements and Guidelines. Geneva: ISO.
- [4] De Menna, F., Loubiere, M., Dietershagen, J., Unger, N., Vittuari, M. (2016). Methodology for evaluating LCC. ReFresh Project, WP5 Deliverable. Available at https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH_D5_2_Meth_for_ev_LCC_Final_formatted_0.pdf
- [5] Vogtländer, J. G.; Brezet, H. C.; Hendriks, C. F. (2001). The virtual eco-cost '99: A single LCA-based indicator for sustainability and the eco-costs–value ratio (EVR) model. The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, 6(3), 157–166; <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02978734>
- [6] Vogtländer, J. G., Bijma, A., Brezet, H. C. (2002). Communicating the eco-efficiency of products and services by means of the eco-costs/value model. Journal of Cleaner Production, 10(1), 57–67; [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-6526\(01\)00013-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-6526(01)00013-0).
- [7] Vogtländer, J. G., Mestre, A. C. (2009). The eco-costs/value ratio for quantitative, LCA based, assessment of sustainability. In II International Conference on Sustainability Measurement and Modelling ICSMM (Vol. 9).
- [8] Vogtlander, J. G., Scheepens, A. E., Bocken, N. M., Peck, D. (2017). Combined analyses of costs, market value and eco-costs in circular business models: eco-efficient value creation in remanufacturing. Journal of Remanufacturing, 7(1), 1-17; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13243-017-0031-9>.
- [9] Hendriks, C. F., Vogtländer, J. G., Janssen, G. M. T. (2006). The eco-costs/value ratio: A tool to determine the long-term strategy for delinking economy and environmental ecology. International journal of Ecodynamics, 1(2), 136-148; <https://doi.org/10.2495/eco-v1-n2-136-148>.
- [10] Peng, W., Su, D., Wang, S. (2021). Development of an innovative ICT infrastructure for an eco-cost system with life cycle assessment. Sustainability, 13(6), 3118; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063118>.
- [11] Wang, S.; Su, D. (2022). Sustainable product innovation and consumer communication. Sustainability, 14(14), 8395; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148395>.

- [12] Amadei, A. M., De Laurentiis, V., Sala, S. (2021). A review of monetary valuation in life cycle assessment: State of the art and future needs. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 329, 129668; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129668>.
- [13] Smith, M., Moerenhout, J., Thuring, A., de Regel, S., Altmann, A. (2020). Final Report - External Costs; Energy costs, taxes and the impact of government interventions on investments. European Commission, DG ENERGY UNIT A.4; <https://doi.org/10.2833/81390>.
- [14] Rowley-Neale, S. J., Randviir, E. P., Abo Dena, A. S., Banks, C. E. (2018). An overview of recent applications of reduced graphene oxide as a basis of electroanalytical sensing platforms, *Applied Materials Today*, 10 218–226; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2017.11.010>.
- [15] Yang, G., Li, L., Lee, W.B., Ng, M.C. (2018). Structure of graphene and its disorders: a review. *Science and Technology of Advanced Materials*, 19(1), 613–648; <https://doi.org/10.1080/14686996.2018.1494493>.
- [16] The Graphene Council. (2024). Applications. The Graphene Council. <http://www.thegraphenecouncil.org>.
- [17] Soldano, C., Mahmood, A., Dujardin, E. (2010). Production, properties and potential of graphene. *Carbon*, 48(8), 2127-2150; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2010.01.058>.
- [18] Urade, A.R., Lahiri, I., Suresh, K.S. (2022). Graphene properties, synthesis and applications: A review. *JOM*, 75(3), 614–626; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-022-05505-8>.
- [19] Qamar, S., Ramzan, N., Aleem, W. (2024). Graphene dispersion, functionalization techniques and applications: A review. *Synthetic Metals*, 307, 117697; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.synthmet.2024.117697>.
- [20] Canova, C. (2015). Graphene: Properties, synthesis and applications (Bachelor's Thesis, University of Bologna).
- [21] Mbayachi, V. B., Ndayiragije, E., Sammani, T., Taj, S., Mbuta, E. R. (2021). Graphene synthesis, characterization and its applications: A review. *Results in Chemistry*, 3, 100163; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2021.100163>.
- [22] Yang, K., Wu, C., Zhang, G. (2024). A state of review for graphene-based materials in preparation methods, characterization, and properties. *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, 310, 117698; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2024.117698>.
- [23] Al Faruque, M. A., Syduzzaman, M., Sarkar, J., Bilisik, K., Naebe, M. (2021). A review on the production methods and applications of graphene-based materials. *Nanomaterials*, 11(9), 2414; <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11092414>.
- [24] Kanti, P. K., HG, P. K., Wanatasanappan, V. V., Kumar, A., Regasa, M. B. (2025). Graphene's Frontier in aerospace: current applications, challenges, and future directions for space engineering. *Nanoscale Advances*, 7(12), 3603-3618; <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4NA00934G>.

- [25] Liu, J., Bao, S., Wang, X. (2022). Applications of graphene-based materials in sensors: A review. *Micromachines*, 13(2), 184; <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi13020184>.
- [26] Lalire, T., Longuet, C., Taguet, A. (2024). Electrical properties of graphene/multiphase polymer nanocomposites: A review. *Carbon*, 225, 119055; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2024.119055>.
- [27] Moradi, S., Nargesi Azam, F., Abdollahi, H., Rajabifar, N., Rostami, A., Guzman, P., Davachi, S. M. (2025). Graphene-based polymeric microneedles for biomedical applications: a comprehensive review. *ACS Applied Bio Materials*, 8(3), 1835-1861; <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsabm.4c01884>.
- [28] Pryce, D., Alsharrah, F., Khalil, A. M., Kapelan, Z., Memon, F. A. (2022). Comparative life-cycle cost analysis of alternative technologies for the removal of emerging contaminants from urban wastewater. *Water*, 14(12), 1919; <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14121919>.
- [29] Arvidsson, R., Kushnir, D., Sandén, B.A., Molander, S. (2014). Prospective life cycle assessment of graphene production by ultrasonication and chemical reduction. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 48(8), 4529–4536; <https://doi.org/10.1021/es405338k>.
- [30] Munuera, J., Britnell, L., Santoro, C., Cuéllar-Franca, R., Casiraghi, C. (2021). A review on sustainable production of graphene and related life cycle assessment. *2D Materials*, 9(1), 012002; <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1583/ac3f23>.
- [31] Pitaro, F., Seeger, S., Nowack, B. (2025). The Safe and Sustainable by Design framework applied to graphene-based materials. *Environment International*, 197, 109345; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109345>.
- [32] Wang, Z. L. (2013). Triboelectric nanogenerators as new energy technology for self-powered systems and as active mechanical and chemical sensors. *ACS nano*, 7(11), 9533-9557; <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn404614z>.
- [33] Ashton, K. (2009). That 'internet of things' thing. *RFID journal*, 22(7), 97-114.
- [34] Gubbi, J., Buyya, R., Marusic, S., Palaniswami, M. (2013). Internet of Things (IoT): A vision, architectural elements, and future directions. *Future generation computer systems*, 29(7), 1645-1660; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2013.01.010>.
- [35] Ganguly, S., Sengupta, J. (2024). Graphene-based nanotechnology in the Internet of Things: a mini review. *Discover Nano*, 19(1), 110; <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11671-024-04054-0>.
- [36] Ahmed, A., Hassan, I., Ibn-Mohammed, T., Mostafa, H., Reaney, I. M., Koh, L. S., Wang, Z. L. (2017). Environmental life cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis of triboelectric nanogenerators. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 10(3), 653-671; <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7EE00158D>.

- [37] Hatta, F. F., Mohammad Haniff, M. A. S., Mohamed, M. A. (2022). A review on applications of graphene in triboelectric nanogenerators. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 46(2), 544-576; <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.7245>.
- [38] Xie, B., Guo, Y., Chen, Y., Zhang, H., Xiao, J., Hou, M., Wong, C. (2025). Advances in graphene-based electrode for triboelectric nanogenerator. *Nano-Micro Letters*, 17(1), 17; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-024-01530-1>.
- [39] Xiong, Y., Luo, L., Yang, J., Han, J., Liu, Y., Jiao, H., Sun, Q. (2023). Scalable spinning, winding, and knitting graphene textile TENG for energy harvesting and human motion recognition. *Nano Energy*, 107, 108137; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2022.108137>.
- [40] Ali, I., Dulal, M., Karim, N., Afroj, S. (2024). 2D material-based wearable energy harvesting textiles: a review. *Small Structures*, 5(1), 2300282; <https://doi.org/10.1002/sstr.202300282>.
- [41] Azani, M.-R., Hassanpour, A. (2024). Electronic textiles (E-Textiles): Types, fabrication methods, and recent strategies to overcome durability challenges (washability & flexibility). *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics*, 35, 1897; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-024-13347-0>.
- [42] Beeby, S.P., Torah, R.N., Wagih, M., Isaia, B., Black, S., Saunders, J., Yang, K. (2024). Heterogeneous E-Textiles: Materials, Manufacturing and Sustainability. *Advanced Materials Technologies*, 10(1), 2400844; <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202400844>.
- [43] Dulal, M., Afroj, S., Ahn, J., Cho, Y., Carr, C., Kim, I.-D., Karim, N. (2022). Toward Sustainable Wearable Electronic Textiles. *ACS Nano*, 16(12), 19755–19788; <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.2c07723>.
- [44] Dulal, M., Modha, H. R. M., Liu, J., Islam, M. R., Carr, C., Hasan, T., Thorn, R. M. S., Afroj, S., Karim, N. (2024). Sustainable, Wearable, and Eco-Friendly Electronic Textiles. *Energy & Environmental Materials*, 8(1), e12854; <https://doi.org/10.1002/eem2.12854>.
- [45] Dulal, M., Afroj, S., Islam, M.R., Zhang, M., Yang, Y., Hu, H., Novoselov, K.S., Karim, N. (2024). Closed-Loop Recycling of Wearable Electronic Textiles. *Small*, 20(22), 2407207; <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202407207>.
- [46] van der Velden, N.M., Kuusk, K., Köhler, A.R. (2015). Life cycle assessment and eco-design of smart textiles: The importance of material selection demonstrated through e-textile product redesign. *Materials & Design*, 84, 313–324; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2015.06.129>.
- [47] Zhu, J., Cho, M., Li, Y., He, T., Ahn, J., Park, J., Ren, T.-L., Lee, C., Park, I. (2021). Machine learning-enabled textile-based graphene gas sensing with energy harvesting-assisted IoT application. *Nano Energy*, 86, 106035; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.106035>.
- [48] Zhu, S.; Liu, X. (2025). The Ecodesign Transformation of Smart Clothing: Towards a Systemic and Coupled Social–Ecological–Technological System Perspective. *Sustainability*, 17(5), 2102; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17052102>.

- [49] Passerini, S.; Barelli, L.; Baumann, M.; Peters, J.F.; Weil, M. (2024). Emerging battery technologies to boost the clean energy transition: Cost, sustainability, and performance analysis. Springer; <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48359-2>.
- [50] Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC.
- [51] Zackrisson, M., Avellán, L., Orlenius, J. (2010). Life cycle assessment of lithium-ion batteries. Journal of Cleaner Production, 18, 15, 1519-1529; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2010.06.004>.
- [52] Yu, Y., Chen, B., Huang, K., Wang, X., Wang, D. (2014). Environmental impact assessment and end-of-life treatment policy analysis for Li-ion batteries and Ni-MH batteries. International journal of environmental research and public health, 11(3), 3185-3198; <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph110303185>.
- [53] Zackrisson, M., Fransson, K., Hildenbrand, J., Lampic, G., O'Dwyer, C. (2016). Life cycle assessment of lithium-air battery cells. Journal of Cleaner Production, 135, 299-311; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.104>.
- [54] Liang, L., Su, J., Xia, B., Yu, Y., Ji, D., Sun, Y., Cui, S., Zhu, J. (2017). Life cycle assessment of lithium-ion batteries for greenhouse gas emissions. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 117, 285-293; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.08.028>.
- [55] Ellingsen, L.A.-W., Hung, C.R., Strømman, A.H. (2017). Identifying key assumptions and differences in life cycle assessment studies of lithium-ion traction batteries with focus on greenhouse gas emissions. Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment, 55, 82-90; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.06.028>.
- [56] Peters, J. F., Baumann, M., Zimmermann, B., Braun, J., Weil, M. (2017). The environmental impact of Li-Ion batteries and the role of key parameters—A review. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 67, 491-506; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.08.039>.
- [57] Peters, J. F., Weil, M. (2018). Providing a common base for life cycle assessments of Li-Ion batteries. Journal of Cleaner Production, 171, 704-713; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.016>.
- [58] Raugei, M., Winfield, P. (2019). Prospective LCA of the production and EoL recycling of a novel type of Li-ion battery for electric vehicles. Journal of cleaner production, 213, 926-932; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.237>.
- [59] Dai, Q., Kelly, J. C., Gaines, L., Wang, M. (2019). Life cycle analysis of lithium-ion batteries for automotive applications. Batteries, 5(2), 48; <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries5020048>.
- [60] Cerdas, F., Titscher, P., Bognar, N., Schmuch, R., Winter, M., Kwade, A., Herrmann, C. (2018). Exploring the effect of increased energy density on the environmental impacts of traction batteries: A comparison of energy optimized lithium-ion and lithium-sulfur batteries for mobility applications. Energies, 11(1), 150; <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11010150>.

- [61] da Silva Lima, L., Quartier, M., Buchmayr, A., Sanjuan-Delmás, D., Laget, H., Corbisier, D., Mertens, J., Dewulf, J. (2021). Life cycle assessment of lithium-ion batteries and vanadium redox flow batteries-based renewable energy storage systems. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 46, 101286; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101286>.
- [62] Sadhukhan, J., Christensen, M. (2021). An in-depth life cycle assessment (LCA) of lithium-ion battery for climate impact mitigation strategies. *Energies*, 14(17), 5555; <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14175555>.
- [63] Chen, Q., Lai, X., Gu, H., Tang, X., Gao, F., Han, X., Zheng, Y. (2022). Investigating carbon footprint and carbon reduction potential using a cradle-to-cradle LCA approach on lithium-ion batteries for electric vehicles in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 369, 133342; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133342>.
- [64] Kallitsis, E., Korre, A., Kelsall, G. H. (2022). Life cycle assessment of recycling options for automotive Li-ion battery packs. *Journal of cleaner production*, 371, 133636; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133636>.
- [65] Benveniste, G., Sánchez, A., Rallo, H., Corchero, C., Amante, B. (2022). Comparative life cycle assessment of Li-Sulphur and Li-ion batteries for electric vehicles. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances*, 15, 200086; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2022.200086>.
- [66] Porzio, J., Scown, C. D. (2021). Life-cycle assessment considerations for batteries and battery materials. *Advanced Energy Materials*, 11(33), 2100771; <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202100771>.
- [67] Chordia, M., Nordelöf, A., Ellingsen, L.A.-W. (2022). Environmental life cycle implications of upscaling lithium-ion battery production. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 26, 2024–2039; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01976-0>.
- [68] Erakca, M., Bautista, S. P., Moghaddas, S., Baumann, M., Bauer, W., Leuthner, L., Weil, M. (2023). Closing gaps in LCA of lithium-ion batteries: LCA of lab-scale cell production with new primary data. *Journal of cleaner production*, 384, 135510; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135510>.
- [69] Marashli, A., Al-Kassab, A. I., Gab-Allah, D. M., Shalby, M., Salah, A. (2024). Numerical life cycle assessment of lithium ion battery, Li-NMC type, integrated with PV system. *Results in Engineering*, 23, 102489; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102489>.
- [70] Paul, D.; Pechancová, V.; Saha, N.; Pavelková, D.; Saha, N.; Motiei, M.; Jamatia, T.; Chaudhuri, M.; Ivanichenko, A.; Venher, M.; Hrbáčková, L.; Saha, P. (2024). Life cycle assessment of lithium-based batteries: Review of sustainability dimensions. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 206, 114860; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114860>.
- [71] Accardo, A., Gentilucci, G., Pontone, L., & Spessa, E. (2025). Investigating Life Cycle Cost, Environmental and Social Impacts of a Lithium-ion Battery Pack. *IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology*; <https://doi.org/10.1109/OJVT.2025.3579221>.

- [72] Wu, Z., Kong, D., (2018) Comparative life cycle assessment of lithium-ion batteries with lithium metal, silicon nanowire, and graphite anodes. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 20, 1233–1244; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-018-1548-9>.
- [73] Lai, X., Chen, Q., Tang, X., Zhou, Y., Gao, F., Guo, Y., Zheng, Y. (2022). Critical review of life cycle assessment of lithium-ion batteries for electric vehicles: A lifespan perspective. *Etransportation*, 12, 100169; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etrans.2022.100169>.
- [74] Pellow, M. A., Ambrose, H., Mulvaney, D., Betita, R., Shaw, S. (2020). Research gaps in environmental life cycle assessments of lithium ion batteries for grid-scale stationary energy storage systems: End-of-life options and other issues. *Sustainable Materials and Technologies*, 23, e00120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2019.e00120>
- [75] Domingues, A. M., de Souza, R. G. (2024). Review of life cycle assessment on lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) recycling. *Next Sustainability*, 3, 100032; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nxsust.2024.100032>.
- [76] Zhou, H., Li, W., Poulet, T., Basarir, H., Karrech, A. (2024). Life cycle assessment of recycling lithium-ion battery related mineral processing by-products: A review. *Minerals Engineering*, 208, 108600; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2024.108600>.
- [77] European Commission. (2013). Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) Guide (Version 3.1). Green Forum. https://green-forum.ec.europa.eu/green-business/environmental-footprint-methods/life-cycle-assessment-ef-methods_en.
- [78] Sala, S., Cerutti, A. K., Pant, R., European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC). (2021). EF 3.1 – Life Cycle Impact Assessment method: Updates and characterization factors (JRC130796). Publications Office of the European Union. https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC130796/JRC130796_01.pdf.
- [79] Pré Sustainability. (2023). SimaPro Database Manual: Methods. SimaPro. <https://simapro.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/DatabaseManualMethods.pdf>.
- [80] Frischknecht, R., Jolliet, O. (2005, updated 2016). Description of LCIA methods. Operational guide to the ISO-standards for life cycle impact assessment methods. ESU-services Ltd. Available at <https://esu-services.ch/fileadmin/download/tender/ESU-Description-of-LCIAmethods.pdf>.
- [81] Degen, F., Schütte, M. (2022). Life cycle assessment of the energy consumption and GHG emissions of state-of-the-art automotive battery cell production. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 330, 129798; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129798>.

- [82] Bahmei, F., Bahramifar, N., Ghasemi, S., Younesi, H., Weil, M. (2025). Comparison of environmental impacts in the production of graphene from biomass waste and the Hummers' method. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 497, 145145; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.145145>.
- [83] Serrano-Luján, L., Víctor-Román, S., Toledo, C., Sanahuja-Parejo, O., Mansour, A. E., Abad, J., Amassian, A., Benito, A. M., Maser, W. K., Urbina, A. (2019). Environmental impact of the production of graphene oxide and reduced graphene oxide. *SN Applied Sciences*, 1; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-0193-1>.

PENDING FOR EC APPROVAL

7 Appendix

The following **Tables (14-23)** report the detailed results of the LCA assessments performed.

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Raw Materials				Consumables					PPE			Transport		
		Tap water	h-rGO	Fibre, polyester	Silicone product	Tissue paper	Isopropyl acetate	Acetone liquid	Tap water	Polypropylene granulate	Synthetic rubber	Polypropylene granulate	Polypropylene granulate	Transport aircraft	Transport lorry	Transport lorry
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	1.78E+00	3.87E-06	1.58E+00	8.06E-03	8.83E-03	1.00E-03	1.06E-02	5.09E-03	3.20E-06	4.80E-05	6.87E-04	9.60E-04	9.04E-04	1.74E-04	9.90E-07	5.70E-04
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	9.30E+01	6.73E-04	6.10E+01	2.10E+00	1.60E+00	1.45E-01	1.63E+00	9.28E-01	5.56E-04	1.26E-02	1.15E-01	2.51E-01	2.37E-01	3.59E-02	2.80E-04	1.61E-01
Fex (CTUe)	4.33E+04	2.20E-03	4.32E+04	7.13E+00	1.43E+01	8.84E-01	8.12E+00	7.41E-01	1.82E-03	3.87E-03	5.87E-01	7.73E-02	7.28E-02	1.34E-01	1.13E-03	6.52E-01
PM (disease inc.)	5.03E-06	1.63E-11	4.09E-06	8.24E-08	8.73E-08	1.19E-08	9.73E-08	4.58E-08	1.35E-11	5.59E-10	8.72E-09	1.12E-08	1.05E-08	5.56E-10	3.23E-11	1.86E-08
ME (kg N eq)	6.63E-01	4.82E-07	6.44E-01	1.57E-03	1.26E-03	2.08E-04	1.23E-03	7.64E-04	3.98E-07	9.10E-06	9.04E-05	1.82E-04	1.71E-04	5.93E-05	3.09E-07	1.78E-04
Fe (kg P eq)	2.08E-02	5.08E-08	1.47E-02	1.12E-04	6.33E-05	7.54E-06	3.97E-05	5.32E-05	4.21E-08	2.61E-07	2.90E-06	5.22E-06	4.91E-06	3.22E-08	3.39E-10	1.95E-07
TE (mol N eq)	7.12E+00	5.21E-06	6.93E+00	1.56E-02	1.37E-02	1.64E-03	1.35E-02	8.35E-03	4.31E-06	9.75E-05	1.01E-03	1.95E-03	1.84E-03	6.49E-04	3.39E-06	1.95E-03
HTC (CTUh)	1.05E-06	1.80E-13	1.05E-06	3.02E-10	9.37E-10	1.15E-10	2.36E-10	9.52E-11	1.49E-13	8.67E-13	1.72E-11	1.73E-11	1.63E-11	1.55E-11	2.38E-14	1.37E-11
HTNC (CTUh)	1.16E-06	4.62E-12	9.44E-07	9.90E-09	1.10E-08	3.88E-09	8.24E-09	1.55E-09	3.82E-12	1.54E-11	3.97E-10	3.07E-10	2.89E-10	3.63E-11	3.22E-12	1.86E-09
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	2.81E+00	8.29E-05	1.38E+00	4.74E-02	6.46E-02	7.18E-01	8.43E-02	1.14E-03	6.86E-05	2.52E-05	1.07E-02	5.05E-04	4.75E-04	2.30E-03	1.79E-05	1.03E-02
LU (Pt)	7.28E+01	1.86E-03	3.23E+01	1.51E+00	5.69E+00	5.00E+00	2.69E+00	1.11E-02	1.54E-03	1.58E-04	2.90E-01	3.16E-03	2.97E-03	1.79E-03	2.23E-05	1.28E-02
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	9.28E-06	2.89E-11	1.06E-06	7.29E-06	6.59E-07	3.69E-09	1.47E-08	2.74E-10	2.39E-11	3.61E-12	7.93E-10	7.22E-11	6.79E-11	1.20E-11	1.23E-13	7.10E-11
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.74E+00	1.52E-06	1.66E+00	1.10E-02	4.61E-03	5.92E-04	1.11E-02	3.70E-03	1.26E-06	4.90E-05	4.43E-04	9.80E-04	9.22E-04	1.79E-04	9.42E-07	5.43E-04
RU-fos (MJ)	1.41E+03	1.23E-02	8.92E+02	4.21E+01	2.66E+01	1.43E+01	3.47E+01	2.47E+01	1.02E-02	4.24E-01	3.32E+00	8.47E+00	7.98E+00	5.20E-01	4.03E-03	2.32E+00
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	3.12E-05	3.01E-10	2.03E-05	1.40E-06	2.45E-06	1.06E-07	2.89E-07	1.84E-07	2.49E-10	2.52E-10	3.07E-06	5.04E-09	4.75E-09	1.38E-10	9.44E-13	5.44E-10
WU (m ³ depriv.)	2.49E+01	1.04E-01	1.60E+01	4.62E-01	2.31E+00	1.44E+00	1.19E+00	5.27E-01	8.64E-02	4.03E-03	6.52E-02	8.07E-02	7.60E-02	2.27E-03	1.75E-05	1.01E-02

Table 14 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 1

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Packaging & Storage		Spraying Process-Preparation		Laser Process	Waste Management			
		Packaging film, low density polyethylene	Corrugated board box	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Wastewater	Waste rubber	Waste graphical paper	Waste plastic
AP (molH ⁺ eq)	1.78E+00	2.96E-03	2.13E-03	3.58E-03	1.32E-02	1.41E-01	1.38E-06	1.62E-05	7.98E-05	2.19E-04
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	9.30E+01	5.86E-01	3.24E-01	5.20E-01	1.91E+00	2.05E+01	2.74E-04	1.26E-01	1.48E-01	6.67E-01
Fex (CTUe)	4.33E+04	5.35E-01	1.72E+00	2.38E+00	8.76E+00	9.38E+01	8.64E-02	2.27E-01	1.05E+00	1.97E+00
PM (disease inc.)	5.03E-06	3.13E-08	2.06E-08	1.17E-08	4.32E-08	4.63E-07	1.09E-11	6.96E-11	6.66E-10	1.52E-09
ME (kg N eq)	6.63E-01	4.76E-04	6.12E-04	2.59E-04	9.54E-04	1.02E-02	1.58E-05	6.64E-06	1.02E-04	1.12E-04
Fe (kg P eq)	2.08E-02	5.53E-06	1.67E-05	1.31E-04	4.81E-04	5.15E-03	1.54E-06	1.84E-08	2.15E-07	1.36E-07
TE (mol N eq)	7.12E+00	5.20E-03	3.97E-03	2.71E-03	9.98E-03	1.07E-01	4.55E-06	7.32E-05	3.50E-04	1.08E-03
HTC (CTUh)	1.05E-06	8.27E-11	1.47E-10	7.68E-11	2.82E-10	3.03E-09	3.14E-13	1.29E-12	2.23E-11	2.32E-10
HTNC (CTUh)	1.16E-06	1.31E-09	3.33E-09	3.87E-09	1.42E-08	1.53E-07	5.80E-11	3.09E-11	1.06E-09	2.81E-09
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	2.81E+00	1.16E-02	1.21E-02	1.06E-02	3.89E-02	4.17E-01	1.93E-05	2.19E-05	2.78E-05	7.28E-05
LU (Pt)	7.28E+01	1.67E+00	1.20E+01	2.57E-01	9.46E-01	1.01E+01	8.45E-04	1.84E-03	6.68E-02	1.46E-01
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	9.28E-06	1.93E-09	2.83E-09	5.48E-09	2.02E-08	2.16E-07	2.65E-12	2.82E-11	1.19E-10	3.19E-10
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.74E+00	2.44E-03	1.03E-03	9.00E-04	3.31E-03	3.55E-02	8.23E-07	1.85E-05	1.50E-04	3.14E-04
RU-fos (MJ)	1.41E+03	1.69E+01	4.24E+00	7.50E+00	2.76E+01	2.96E+02	3.08E-03	1.29E-02	7.78E-02	1.91E-01
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	3.12E-05	4.92E-08	1.15E-06	4.97E-08	1.83E-07	1.96E-06	6.18E-10	3.73E-10	2.15E-09	7.87E-09
WU (m ³ depriv.)	2.49E+01	3.29E-01	7.17E-02	4.93E-02	1.81E-01	1.94E+00	-4.29E-02	4.41E-04	-9.59E-03	-2.12E-03

Table 15 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 2

Damage Category (Unit)	Raw Materials				Consumables					PPE			Transport		
	Tap water	h-rGO	Fibre polyester	Silicone product	Tissue paper	Isopropyl acetate	Acetone liquid	Tap water	Polypropylene granulate	Synthetic rubber	Polypropylene granulate	Polypropylene granulate	Transport aircraft	Transport lorry	Transport lorry
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	0.00%	88.75%	0.45%	0.50%	0.06%	0.59%	0.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.04%	0.05%	0.05%	0.01%	0.00%	0.03%
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	0.00%	65.59%	2.26%	1.72%	0.16%	1.75%	1.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.12%	0.27%	0.25%	0.04%	0.00%	0.17%
Fex (CTUe)	0.00%	99.67%	0.02%	0.03%	0.00%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
PM (disease inc.)	0.00%	81.18%	1.64%	1.73%	0.24%	1.93%	0.91%	0.00%	0.01%	0.17%	0.22%	0.21%	0.01%	0.00%	0.37%
ME (kg N eq)	0.00%	97.21%	0.24%	0.19%	0.03%	0.19%	0.12%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%	0.03%	0.01%	0.00%	0.03%
Fe (kg P eq)	0.00%	70.78%	0.54%	0.30%	0.04%	0.19%	0.26%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
TE (mol N eq)	0.00%	97.32%	0.22%	0.19%	0.02%	0.19%	0.12%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%	0.03%	0.01%	0.00%	0.03%
HTC (CTUh)	0.00%	99.47%	0.03%	0.09%	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
HTNC (CTUh)	0.00%	81.32%	0.85%	0.94%	0.33%	0.71%	0.13%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.03%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.16%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	0.00%	49.12%	1.68%	2.30%	25.54%	3.00%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.38%	0.02%	0.02%	0.08%	0.00%	0.37%
LU (Pt)	0.00%	44.44%	2.08%	7.82%	6.87%	3.69%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.40%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	0.00%	11.47%	78.56%	7.10%	0.04%	0.16%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	0.00%	95.52%	0.63%	0.27%	0.03%	0.64%	0.21%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.06%	0.05%	0.01%	0.00%	0.03%
RU-fos (MJ)	0.00%	63.29%	2.99%	1.88%	1.01%	2.46%	1.75%	0.00%	0.03%	0.24%	0.60%	0.57%	0.04%	0.00%	0.16%

RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	0.00%	65.06%	4.47%	7.86%	0.34%	0.92%	0.59%	0.00%	0.00%	9.83%	0.02%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	0.42%	64.37%	1.86%	9.26%	5.77%	4.79%	2.11%	0.35%	0.02%	0.26%	0.32%	0.31%	0.01%	0.00%	0.04%

Table 16 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 1

Damage Category (Unit)	Packaging & Storage		Spraying Process- Preparation		Laser Process	Waste Management			
	Packaging film, low density polyethylene	Corrugated board box	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Wastewater	Waste rubber	Waste graphical paper	Waste plastic
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	0.17%	0.12%	0.20%	0.74%	7.94%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	0.63%	0.35%	0.56%	2.06%	22.04%	0.00%	0.14%	0.16%	0.72%
Fex (CTUe)	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.02%	0.22%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
PM (disease inc.)	0.62%	0.41%	0.23%	0.86%	9.20%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%
ME (kg N eq)	0.07%	0.09%	0.04%	0.14%	1.54%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.02%
Fe (kg P eq)	0.03%	0.08%	0.63%	2.31%	24.77%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
TE (mol N eq)	0.07%	0.06%	0.04%	0.14%	1.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%
HTC (CTUh)	0.01%	0.01%	0.01%	0.03%	0.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%
HTNC (CTUh)	0.11%	0.29%	0.33%	1.23%	13.15%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%	0.24%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	0.41%	0.43%	0.38%	1.38%	14.84%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
LU (Pt)	2.29%	16.48%	0.35%	1.30%	13.93%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%	0.20%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	0.02%	0.03%	0.06%	0.22%	2.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

POF (kg NMVOC eq)	0.14%	0.06%	0.05%	0.19%	2.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.02%
RU-fos (MJ)	1.20%	0.30%	0.53%	1.96%	20.97%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.01%
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	0.16%	3.68%	0.16%	0.59%	6.28%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.32%	0.29%	0.20%	0.73%	7.80%	-0.17%	0.00%	-0.04%	-0.01%

Table 17 - Detailed results for rGO treated textile LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 2

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Raw Materials												Consumables				
		Carbon black	Synthetic rubber	Alkylbenzene sulfonate, linear, petrochemical	Tap water	Copper, cathode	Packaging film, low density polyethylene	Cathode, NCA, for Li-ion battery	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Sheet rolling, aluminium	Lithium hexafluoro-phosphate	Nickel, 99.5%	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Tissue paper	Isopropyl acetate	Acetone liquid	Tap water	Tissue paper
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	6.53E-03	1.61E-02	6.83E-04	3.00E-05	7.98E-01	6.66E-03	6.24E-01	4.84E-01	1.35E-02	1.30E+00	1.06E-01	3.87E-03	5.61E-06	1.47E-04	7.11E-05	1.12E-08	5.61E-06
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	1.36E+00	2.70E+00	9.26E-02	5.21E-03	1.11E+01	1.32E+00	6.13E+01	4.65E+01	1.64E+00	9.51E+01	5.77E-01	3.72E-01	8.09E-04	2.27E-02	1.30E-02	1.94E-06	8.09E-04
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	1.21E+01	1.38E+01	2.89E-01	1.70E-02	2.02E+02	1.21E+00	6.19E+02	9.87E+01	4.88E+00	4.99E+02	4.47E+00	7.90E-01	4.94E-03	1.13E-01	1.03E-02	6.35E-06	4.94E-03
PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	1.58E-07	2.05E-07	8.58E-09	1.26E-10	1.92E-06	7.04E-08	4.83E-06	6.17E-06	1.29E-07	9.10E-06	1.37E-07	4.93E-08	6.64E-11	1.36E-09	6.40E-10	4.72E-14	6.64E-11
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	6.84E-04	2.12E-03	9.39E-05	3.73E-06	3.93E-02	1.07E-03	8.11E-02	5.11E-02	1.51E-03	1.33E-01	1.44E-03	4.09E-04	1.16E-06	1.72E-05	1.07E-05	1.39E-09	1.16E-06
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	1.32E-06	6.80E-05	2.60E-06	3.93E-07	6.57E-02	1.25E-05	5.94E-03	1.41E-03	5.80E-05	7.65E-03	8.19E-04	1.13E-05	4.21E-08	5.53E-07	7.44E-07	1.47E-10	4.21E-08
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	7.53E-03	2.37E-02	1.02E-03	4.03E-05	4.94E-01	1.17E-02	7.86E-01	5.65E-01	1.65E-02	1.26E+00	2.08E-02	4.52E-03	9.18E-06	1.89E-04	1.17E-04	1.50E-08	9.18E-06
HCT (CTUh)	2.13E-07	2.37E-11	4.04E-10	2.50E-10	1.39E-12	8.59E-08	1.86E-10	5.87E-08	4.49E-08	5.86E-10	1.90E-08	5.79E-10	3.59E-10	6.44E-13	3.29E-12	1.33E-12	5.20E-16	6.44E-13
HCNT (CTUh)	1.11E-05	2.18E-09	9.32E-09	2.76E-09	3.58E-11	7.66E-06	2.94E-09	1.56E-06	8.26E-07	1.23E-08	8.32E-07	2.46E-08	6.60E-09	2.17E-11	1.15E-10	2.17E-11	1.33E-14	2.17E-11
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	2.08E-01	2.52E-01	2.40E-03	6.42E-04	6.15E-01	2.62E-02	8.55E+00	5.73E-01	7.22E-02	7.30E+00	4.76E-02	4.58E-03	4.01E-03	1.18E-03	1.59E-05	2.39E-07	4.01E-03
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	1.10E-01	6.79E+00	1.52E-01	1.44E-02	1.15E+02	3.76E+00	1.51E+02	2.65E+01	2.14E+00	2.35E+02	1.04E+00	2.12E-01	2.79E-02	3.75E-02	1.56E-04	5.36E-06	2.79E-02
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	5.61E-10	1.86E-08	6.10E-09	2.24E-10	4.86E-06	4.34E-09	1.31E-06	3.09E-07	1.60E-08	5.32E-06	1.80E-09	2.47E-09	2.06E-11	2.05E-10	3.82E-12	8.35E-14	2.06E-11
POF	1.02E+00	3.11E-03	1.04E-02	4.20E-04	1.18E-05	1.43E-01	5.50E-03	2.32E-01	1.75E-01	6.10E-03	4.06E-01	1.05E-02	1.40E-03	3.31E-06	1.55E-04	5.17E-05	4.39E-09	3.31E-06

(kg NMVOC eq)																			
RU-foss (MJ)	3.45E+03	4.71E+01	7.80E+01	3.07E+00	9.55E-02	1.59E+02	3.81E+01	1.00E+03	4.11E+02	1.97E+01	1.50E+03	7.21E+00	3.29E+00	7.99E-02	4.84E-01	3.45E-01	3.56E-05	7.99E-02	
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	2.64E-09	7.20E-05	3.94E-08	2.33E-09	9.93E-03	1.11E-07	5.88E-03	2.00E-06	2.44E-06	6.77E-04	4.64E-06	1.60E-08	5.92E-10	4.03E-09	2.57E-09	8.68E-13	5.92E-10	
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	-9.21E-03	1.53E+00	4.84E-02	8.08E-01	1.05E+01	7.42E-01	2.59E+02	8.63E+00	4.04E-01	1.09E+02	1.02E+03	6.91E-02	8.02E-03	1.66E-02	7.36E-03	3.02E-04	8.02E-03	

Table 18 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 1

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Slurry preparation					Coating and drying proces	Cell Assembly						Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing			
		Electricity, medium voltage		Electricity, medium voltage	Nitrogen, liquid	Polypropylene, granulate	Electricity, medium voltage										
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	9.02E-05	3.00E-06	2.00E-03	2.79E-03	2.00E-04	6.92E-03	1.00E-05	2.50E-06	1.20E-05	3.50E-03	6.01E-02	1.20E-03	3.57E-06	1.76E-05	1.86E-04	6.01E-04
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	1.31E-02	4.35E-04	2.91E-01	4.04E-01	2.91E-02	1.00E+00	1.45E-03	3.63E-04	1.74E-03	5.07E-01	8.72E+00	1.74E-01	6.98E-04	4.60E-03	2.69E-02	8.72E-02
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	5.98E-02	1.99E-03	1.33E+00	1.85E+00	1.33E-01	4.59E+00	6.64E-03	1.66E-03	7.98E-03	2.32E+00	3.99E+01	7.98E-01	1.88E-03	1.42E-03	1.23E-01	3.99E-01
PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	2.95E-10	9.83E-12	6.57E-09	9.12E-09	6.57E-10	2.26E-08	3.28E-11	8.20E-12	3.93E-11	1.15E-08	1.97E-07	3.93E-09	1.06E-11	2.04E-10	6.08E-10	1.97E-09
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	6.52E-06	2.17E-07	1.45E-04	2.02E-04	1.45E-05	5.00E-04	7.24E-07	1.81E-07	8.69E-07	2.53E-04	4.35E-03	8.69E-05	4.45E-07	3.33E-06	1.34E-05	4.35E-05
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	3.29E-06	1.09E-07	7.31E-05	1.02E-04	7.31E-06	2.52E-04	3.65E-07	9.13E-08	4.38E-07	1.28E-04	2.19E-03	4.38E-05	5.60E-08	9.55E-08	6.77E-06	2.19E-05
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	6.82E-05	2.27E-06	1.52E-03	2.11E-03	1.52E-04	5.23E-03	7.57E-06	1.89E-06	9.09E-06	2.65E-03	4.55E-02	9.09E-04	4.79E-06	3.57E-05	1.40E-04	4.55E-04
HCT (CTUh)	2.13E-07	1.93E-12	6.43E-14	4.29E-11	5.96E-11	4.29E-12	1.48E-10	2.14E-13	5.36E-14	2.57E-13	7.49E-11	1.29E-09	2.57E-11	1.23E-13	3.17E-13	3.98E-12	1.29E-11
HCNT (CTUh)	1.11E-05	9.74E-11	3.24E-12	2.17E-09	3.01E-09	2.17E-10	7.47E-09	1.08E-11	2.70E-12	1.30E-11	3.78E-09	6.50E-08	1.30E-09	3.08E-12	5.62E-12	2.01E-10	6.50E-10
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	2.66E-04	8.85E-06	5.92E-03	8.22E-03	5.92E-04	2.04E-02	2.95E-05	7.39E-06	3.55E-05	1.03E-02	1.77E-01	3.55E-03	9.72E-05	9.23E-06	5.48E-04	1.77E-03
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	6.46E-03	2.15E-04	1.44E-01	2.00E-01	1.44E-02	4.96E-01	7.18E-04	1.79E-04	8.61E-04	2.51E-01	4.31E+00	8.61E-02	1.89E-03	5.78E-05	1.33E-02	4.31E-02
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	1.38E-10	4.58E-12	3.06E-09	4.25E-09	3.06E-10	1.06E-08	1.53E-11	3.82E-12	1.84E-11	5.34E-09	9.19E-08	1.84E-09	2.72E-11	1.32E-12	2.84E-10	9.19E-10
POD (kg NMVOC eq)	1.02E+00	2.26E-05	7.53E-07	5.03E-04	6.99E-04	5.03E-05	1.74E-03	2.51E-06	6.28E-07	3.02E-06	8.78E-04	1.51E-02	3.02E-04	1.39E-06	1.79E-05	4.66E-05	1.51E-04
RU-foss (MJ)	3.45E+03	1.89E-01	6.28E-03	4.19E+00	5.83E+00	4.19E-01	1.45E+01	2.09E-02	5.24E-03	2.51E-02	7.32E+00	1.26E+02	2.51E+00	1.33E-02	1.55E-01	3.88E-01	1.26E+00

RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	1.25E-09	4.16E-11	2.78E-08	3.86E-08	2.78E-09	9.59E-08	1.39E-10	3.47E-11	1.67E-10	4.85E-08	8.34E-07	1.67E-08	6.88E-11	9.23E-11	2.57E-09	8.34E-09
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	1.24E-03	4.12E-05	2.76E-02	3.83E-02	2.76E-03	9.51E-02	1.38E-04	3.44E-05	1.65E-04	4.81E-02	8.27E-01	1.65E-02	1.47E-02	1.48E-03	2.55E-03	8.27E-03

Table 19 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 2

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Degassing			Cells characterization			PPE		Waste				
		Nitrogen, liquid	Polypropylene, granulate	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Synthetic rubber	Polypropylene, granulate	Waste graphical paper	Wastewater	Wastewater	Wastewater	Waste graphical paper
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	3.57E-06	1.76E-05	1.86E-04	6.01E-04	4.21E-03	1.88E-05	4.38E-04	4.47E-04	5.99E-04	1.02E-05	1.02E-05	1.29E-05	5.99E-04
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	6.98E-04	4.60E-03	2.69E-02	8.72E-02	6.10E-01	2.73E-03	7.35E-02	1.17E-01	1.11E+00	2.02E-03	2.03E-03	2.57E-03	1.11E+00
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	1.88E-03	1.42E-03	1.23E-01	3.99E-01	2.80E+00	1.25E-02	3.75E-01	3.61E-02	7.85E+00	6.37E-01	6.40E-01	8.11E-01	7.85E+00
PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	1.06E-11	2.04E-10	6.08E-10	1.97E-09	1.38E-08	6.17E-11	5.56E-09	5.21E-09	5.00E-09	8.06E-11	8.10E-11	1.02E-10	5.00E-09
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	4.45E-07	3.33E-06	1.34E-05	4.35E-05	3.05E-04	1.36E-06	5.77E-05	8.48E-05	7.64E-04	1.16E-04	1.17E-04	1.48E-04	7.64E-04
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	5.60E-08	9.55E-08	6.77E-06	2.19E-05	1.54E-04	6.87E-07	1.85E-06	2.43E-06	1.61E-06	1.14E-05	1.14E-05	1.44E-05	1.61E-06
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	4.79E-06	3.57E-05	1.40E-04	4.55E-04	3.19E-03	1.42E-05	6.44E-04	9.09E-04	2.63E-03	3.36E-05	3.38E-05	4.27E-05	2.63E-03
HCT (CTUh)	2.13E-07	1.23E-13	3.17E-13	3.98E-12	1.29E-11	9.02E-11	4.03E-13	1.10E-11	8.08E-12	1.67E-10	2.32E-12	2.33E-12	2.95E-12	1.67E-10
HCNT (CTUh)	1.11E-05	3.08E-12	5.62E-12	2.01E-10	6.50E-10	4.55E-09	2.03E-11	2.53E-10	1.43E-10	7.97E-09	4.28E-10	4.30E-10	5.44E-10	7.97E-09
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	9.72E-05	9.23E-06	5.48E-04	1.77E-03	1.24E-02	5.56E-05	6.85E-03	2.35E-04	2.09E-04	1.42E-04	1.43E-04	1.81E-04	2.09E-04
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	1.89E-03	5.78E-05	1.33E-02	4.31E-02	3.02E-01	1.35E-03	1.85E-01	1.47E-03	5.01E-01	6.23E-03	6.27E-03	7.93E-03	5.01E-01
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	2.72E-11	1.32E-12	2.84E-10	9.19E-10	6.43E-09	2.88E-11	5.06E-10	3.36E-11	8.96E-10	1.96E-11	1.97E-11	2.49E-11	8.96E-10
POD (kg NMVOC eq)	1.02E+00	1.39E-06	1.79E-05	4.66E-05	1.51E-04	1.06E-03	4.73E-06	2.83E-04	4.57E-04	1.13E-03	6.07E-06	6.10E-06	7.72E-06	1.13E-03
RU-foss (MJ)	3.45E+03	1.33E-02	1.55E-01	3.88E-01	1.26E+00	8.81E+00	3.94E-02	2.12E+00	3.95E+00	5.84E-01	2.27E-02	2.28E-02	2.89E-02	5.84E-01
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	6.88E-11	9.23E-11	2.57E-09	8.34E-09	5.84E-08	2.61E-10	1.96E-06	2.35E-09	1.62E-08	4.56E-09	4.58E-09	5.80E-09	1.62E-08
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	1.47E-02	1.48E-03	2.55E-03	8.27E-03	5.79E-02	2.59E-04	4.16E-02	3.76E-02	-7.20E-02	-3.17E-01	-3.18E-01	-4.03E-01	-7.20E-02

Table 20 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method), Part 3

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Raw materials											Consumables					Slurry preparation						
		Carbon black	Synthetic rubber	Alkylbenzene sulfonate, linear, petrochemical	Tap water	Copper, cathode	Packaging film, low density polyethylene	Cathode, NCA, for Li-ion battery	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Sheet rolling, aluminium	Lithium hexafluorophosphate	Nickel, 99.5%	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Tissue paper	Isopropyl acetate	Acetone, liquid	Tap water	Tissue paper	Electricity, medium voltage					
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	0.19%	0.47%	0.02%	0.00%	23.20%	0.19%	18.14%	14.06%	0.39%	37.67%	3.08%	0.11%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.06%	0.08%	0.01%	
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	0.57%	1.14%	0.04%	0.00%	4.70%	0.56%	25.92%	19.65%	0.69%	40.20%	0.24%	0.16%	0.00%	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.12%	0.17%	0.01%
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	0.79%	0.90%	0.02%	0.00%	13.23%	0.08%	40.46%	6.46%	0.32%	32.61%	0.29%	0.05%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%	0.12%	0.01%
PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	0.68%	0.89%	0.04%	0.00%	8.31%	0.31%	20.96%	26.74%	0.56%	39.44%	0.59%	0.21%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.04%	0.00%
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	0.21%	0.66%	0.03%	0.00%	12.26%	0.33%	25.31%	15.95%	0.47%	41.67%	0.45%	0.13%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.06%	0.00%
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	0.00%	0.08%	0.00%	0.00%	77.52%	0.01%	7.02%	1.67%	0.07%	9.03%	0.97%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%	0.12%	0.01%
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	0.23%	0.73%	0.03%	0.00%	15.17%	0.36%	24.14%	17.34%	0.51%	38.58%	0.64%	0.14%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.06%	0.00%
HCT (CTUh)	2.13E-07	0.01%	0.19%	0.12%	0.00%	40.33%	0.09%	27.56%	21.08%	0.28%	8.90%	0.27%	0.17%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.03%	0.00%
HCNT (CTUh)	1.11E-05	0.02%	0.08%	0.02%	0.00%	69.32%	0.03%	14.16%	7.47%	0.11%	7.53%	0.22%	0.06%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.03%	0.00%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	1.16%	1.41%	0.01%	0.00%	3.43%	0.15%	47.72%	3.20%	0.40%	40.77%	0.27%	0.03%	0.02%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.05%	0.00%
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	0.02%	1.24%	0.03%	0.00%	21.00%	0.68%	27.49%	4.83%	0.39%	42.78%	0.19%	0.04%	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.04%	0.00%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	0.00%	0.16%	0.05%	0.00%	40.55%	0.04%	10.93%	2.58%	0.13%	44.45%	0.02%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.04%	0.00%
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.02E+00	0.31%	1.02%	0.04%	0.00%	14.09%	0.54%	22.81%	17.19%	0.60%	39.87%	1.04%	0.14%	0.00%	0.02%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.07%	0.00%
RU-foss (MJ)	3.45E+03	1.36%	2.26%	0.09%	0.00%	4.60%	1.10%	28.98%	11.90%	0.57%	43.57%	0.21%	0.10%	0.00%	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.12%	0.17%	0.01%
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	0.00%	0.43%	0.00%	0.00%	59.92%	0.00%	35.48%	0.01%	0.01%	4.09%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	0.00%	0.11%	0.00%	0.06%	0.74%	0.05%	18.29%	0.61%	0.03%	7.73%	72.37%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Table 21 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 1

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Coating and drying proces	Cell Assembly						Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing				Degassing			
			Electricity, medium voltage	Nitrogen, liquid	Polypropylene, granulate	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Nitrogen, liquid	Polypropylene, granulate	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage					
AP (molH ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	0.20%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.10%	1.75%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.02%
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	0.42%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.21%	3.69%	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.04%
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	0.30%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.15%	2.61%	0.05%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%
PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	0.10%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.85%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	0.16%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	1.36%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	0.30%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.15%	2.59%	0.05%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.03%
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	0.16%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	1.40%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
HCT (CTUh)	2.13E-07	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.04%	0.60%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
HCNT (CTUh)	1.11E-05	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.59%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	0.11%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.06%	0.99%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	0.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.79%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	0.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.04%	0.77%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.02E+00	0.17%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%	1.48%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
RU-foss (MJ)	3.45E+03	0.42%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.21%	3.64%	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.04%
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.06%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Table 22 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 2

Damage Category (Unit)	Total	Cells characterization		PPE		Waste				
		Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Synthetic rubber	Polypropylene, granulate	Waste graphical paper	Wastewater	Wastewater	Wastewater	Waste graphical paper
AP (mol H ⁺ eq)	3.44E+00	0.12%	0.00%	0.01%	0.01%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%
CC (kg CO ₂ eq)	2.36E+02	0.26%	0.00%	0.03%	0.05%	0.47%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.47%
FEx (CTUe)	1.53E+03	0.18%	0.00%	0.02%	0.00%	0.51%	0.04%	0.04%	0.05%	0.51%
PM (disease inc.)	2.31E-05	0.06%	0.00%	0.02%	0.02%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%
ME (kg N eq)	3.20E-01	0.10%	0.00%	0.02%	0.03%	0.24%	0.04%	0.04%	0.05%	0.24%
FE (kg P eq)	8.47E-02	0.18%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.01%	0.02%	0.00%
TE (mol N eq)	3.26E+00	0.10%	0.00%	0.02%	0.03%	0.08%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%
HCT (CTUh)	2.13E-07	0.04%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.08%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%
HCNT (CTUh)	1.11E-05	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%
IR (kBq U-235 eq)	1.79E+01	0.07%	0.00%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
LU (Pt)	5.49E+02	0.06%	0.00%	0.03%	0.00%	0.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%
OD (kg CFC11 eq)	1.20E-05	0.05%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
POF (kg NMVOC eq)	1.02E+00	0.10%	0.00%	0.03%	0.04%	0.11%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.11%
RU-foss (MJ)	3.45E+03	0.26%	0.00%	0.06%	0.11%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%
RU-mm (kg Sb eq)	1.66E-02	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
WU (m ³ depriv.)	1.41E+03	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	-0.01%	-0.02%	-0.02%	-0.03%	-0.01%

Table 23 - Detailed LIB pouch cell LCA (EF3.1 Method) in percentage (%), Part 3

Evaluation using millipoint (mPt) normalization in SimaPro

In SimaPro, the unit of millipoints (mPt) is used to express the results of LCA. This unit derives from the concept of the point (Pt), which represents the average annual environmental load of a European citizen. In practical terms, one point corresponds to the total normalized and weighted environmental impact caused by an individual in Europe over the course of one year.

Normalization and weighting are essential steps in LCA: normalization allows the comparison of results by relating them to a reference situation (in this case, the average annual impact of a European citizen), while weighting aggregates different impact categories into a single score by assigning relative importance to them. The outcome of this process is a result expressed in points (Pt), which provide an integrated measure of environmental impact across multiple categories.

Since the environmental impacts of most products and processes are considerably smaller than one full point, SimaPro commonly expresses results in mPt, where 1 Pt = 1000 mPt. This convention makes results easier to interpret and compare, avoiding the use of small decimal values.

In summary, the mPt is a practical unit that conveys the normalized and weighted environmental impact of a product or process, always expressed relative to a meaningful benchmark: the annual environmental footprint of an average European inhabitant.

The following **Tables 24-28** shows the SimaPro evaluation with mPt normalization.

Damage Category (Unit: mPt)	Total	Raw Materials				Consumables					PPE			Transport		
		Tap water	h-rGO	Fibre polyester	Silicone product	Tissue paper	Isopropyl acetate	Acetone liquid	Tap water	Polypropylene granulate	Synthetic rubber	Polypropylene granulate	Polypropylene granulate	Transport aircraft	Transport lorry	Transport lorry
Total	2.84E+01	8.24E-04	2.61E+01	1.73E-01	1.43E-01	4.75E-02	1.49E-01	8.29E-02	6.82E-04	1.16E-03	1.50E-02	2.32E-02	2.19E-02	2.50E-03	2.24E-05	1.29E-02
AP	1.99E+00	4.32E-06	1.76E+00	8.99E-03	9.86E-03	1.12E-03	1.18E-02	5.68E-03	3.57E-06	5.35E-05	7.66E-04	1.07E-03	1.01E-03	1.94E-04	1.10E-06	6.36E-04
CC	2.59E+00	1.88E-05	1.70E+00	5.87E-02	4.46E-02	4.04E-03	4.54E-02	2.59E-02	1.55E-05	3.50E-04	3.21E-03	7.00E-03	6.60E-03	1.00E-03	7.81E-06	4.50E-03
Fex	1.47E+01	7.44E-07	1.46E+01	2.41E-03	4.86E-03	2.99E-04	2.75E-03	2.51E-04	6.16E-07	1.31E-06	1.99E-04	2.62E-05	2.47E-05	4.53E-05	3.83E-07	2.21E-04
PM	7.57E-01	2.46E-06	6.15E-01	1.24E-02	1.31E-02	1.79E-03	1.46E-02	6.90E-03	2.03E-06	8.41E-05	1.31E-03	1.68E-03	1.58E-03	8.37E-05	4.86E-06	2.80E-03
ME	1.00E+00	7.30E-07	9.76E-01	2.38E-03	1.91E-03	3.16E-04	1.86E-03	1.16E-03	6.03E-07	1.38E-05	1.37E-04	2.75E-04	2.59E-04	8.98E-05	4.67E-07	2.69E-04
Fe	3.63E-01	8.86E-07	2.57E-01	1.96E-03	1.10E-03	1.31E-04	6.91E-04	9.28E-04	7.33E-07	4.55E-06	5.05E-05	9.09E-05	8.56E-05	5.62E-07	5.91E-09	3.41E-06

TE	1.50E+00	1.09E-06	1.46E+00	3.27E-03	2.87E-03	3.45E-04	2.84E-03	1.75E-03	9.04E-07	2.05E-05	2.12E-04	4.09E-04	3.85E-04	1.36E-04	7.11E-07	4.10E-04
HTC	1.30E+00	2.23E-07	1.30E+00	3.72E-04	1.16E-03	1.42E-04	2.91E-04	1.18E-04	1.84E-07	1.07E-06	2.13E-05	2.14E-05	2.02E-05	1.92E-05	2.93E-08	1.69E-05
HTNC	1.66E-01	6.61E-07	1.35E-01	1.41E-03	1.57E-03	5.54E-04	1.18E-03	2.22E-04	5.46E-07	2.20E-06	5.68E-05	4.39E-05	4.14E-05	5.19E-06	4.60E-07	2.65E-04
IR	3.34E-02	9.84E-07	1.64E-02	5.62E-04	7.66E-04	8.53E-03	1.00E-03	1.36E-05	8.14E-07	2.99E-07	1.27E-04	5.99E-06	5.64E-06	2.74E-05	2.12E-07	1.22E-04
LU	7.05E-03	1.80E-07	3.13E-03	1.47E-04	5.51E-04	4.84E-04	2.60E-04	1.08E-06	1.49E-07	1.53E-08	2.81E-05	3.06E-07	2.88E-07	1.73E-07	2.16E-09	1.24E-06
OD	1.12E-02	3.49E-08	1.28E-03	8.79E-03	7.94E-04	4.44E-06	1.77E-05	3.30E-07	2.88E-08	4.35E-09	9.56E-07	8.70E-08	8.19E-08	1.45E-08	1.48E-10	8.55E-08
POF	2.03E+00	1.78E-06	1.94E+00	1.28E-02	5.40E-03	6.92E-04	1.30E-02	4.33E-03	1.47E-06	5.73E-05	5.19E-04	1.15E-03	1.08E-03	2.10E-04	1.10E-06	6.35E-04
RU-fos	1.80E+00	1.58E-05	1.14E+00	5.39E-02	3.40E-02	1.83E-02	4.45E-02	3.16E-02	1.31E-05	5.42E-04	4.25E-03	1.08E-02	1.02E-02	6.65E-04	5.16E-06	2.97E-03
RU-mm	3.71E-02	3.57E-07	2.41E-02	1.66E-03	2.91E-03	1.26E-04	3.43E-04	2.19E-04	2.95E-07	2.99E-07	3.64E-03	5.98E-06	5.63E-06	1.63E-07	1.12E-09	6.45E-07
WU	1.85E-01	7.75E-04	1.19E-01	3.43E-03	1.71E-02	1.07E-02	8.84E-03	3.91E-03	6.41E-04	2.99E-05	4.84E-04	5.99E-04	5.64E-04	1.69E-05	1.30E-07	7.48E-05

Table 24 - SimaPro evaluation rGO treated textile results with mPt, Part 1

Damage Category (Unit: mPt)	Total	Packaging & Storage		Spraying Process- Preparation		Laser Proces	Waste Management			
		Packaging film, low density polyethylene	Corrugated board box	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage		Electricity, medium voltage	Wastewater	Waste rubber	Waste graphical paper
Total	2.84E+01	5.40E-02	2.76E-02	3.62E-02	1.33E-01	1.43E+00	-2.12E-04	3.68E-03	5.29E-03	2.14E-02
AP	1.99E+00	3.30E-03	2.37E-03	4.00E-03	1.47E-02	1.58E-01	1.54E-06	1.80E-05	8.91E-05	2.44E-04
CC	2.59E+00	1.63E-02	9.04E-03	1.45E-02	5.33E-02	5.71E-01	7.63E-06	3.51E-03	4.13E-03	1.86E-02
Fex	1.47E+01	1.81E-04	5.82E-04	8.05E-04	2.96E-03	3.18E-02	2.92E-05	7.69E-05	3.54E-04	6.66E-04
PM	7.57E-01	4.71E-03	3.10E-03	1.77E-03	6.50E-03	6.97E-02	1.64E-06	1.05E-05	1.00E-04	2.29E-04
ME	1.00E+00	7.20E-04	9.27E-04	3.93E-04	1.45E-03	1.55E-02	2.39E-05	1.01E-05	1.54E-04	1.70E-04
Fe	3.63E-01	9.64E-05	2.90E-04	2.28E-03	8.38E-03	8.98E-02	2.68E-05	3.20E-07	3.75E-06	2.37E-06
TE	1.50E+00	1.09E-03	8.33E-04	5.69E-04	2.09E-03	2.24E-02	9.56E-07	1.54E-05	7.35E-05	2.27E-04
HTC	1.30E+00	1.02E-04	1.81E-04	9.48E-05	3.49E-04	3.74E-03	3.88E-07	1.60E-06	2.75E-05	2.86E-04
HTNC	1.66E-01	1.87E-04	4.76E-04	5.53E-04	2.04E-03	2.18E-02	8.29E-06	4.42E-06	1.52E-04	4.01E-04

IR	3.34E-02	1.38E-04	1.44E-04	1.26E-04	4.62E-04	4.95E-03	2.29E-07	2.60E-07	3.30E-07	8.65E-07
LU	7.05E-03	1.62E-04	1.16E-03	2.49E-05	9.16E-05	9.82E-04	8.19E-08	1.78E-07	6.47E-06	1.41E-05
OD	1.12E-02	2.32E-06	3.42E-06	6.60E-06	2.43E-05	2.60E-04	3.20E-09	3.39E-08	1.44E-07	3.84E-07
POF	2.03E+00	2.86E-03	1.21E-03	1.05E-03	3.87E-03	4.15E-02	9.62E-07	2.16E-05	1.76E-04	3.68E-04
RU-fos	1.80E+00	2.17E-02	5.42E-03	9.60E-03	3.53E-02	3.79E-01	3.94E-06	1.65E-05	9.95E-05	2.44E-04
RU-mm	3.71E-02	5.83E-05	1.36E-03	5.90E-05	2.17E-04	2.33E-03	7.33E-07	4.43E-07	2.56E-06	9.34E-06
WU	1.85E-01	2.44E-03	5.32E-04	3.66E-04	1.35E-03	1.44E-02	-3.19E-04	3.28E-06	-7.12E-05	-1.58E-05

Table 25 - SimaPro evaluation rGO treated textile results with mPt, Part 2

Damage Category (Unit: mPt)	Total	Raw materials												Consumables				Slurry preparation					
		Carbon black	Synthetic rubber	Alkylbenzene sulfonate, linear, petrochemical	Tap water	Copper, cathode	Packaging film, low density polyethylene	Cathode, NCA, for Li-ion battery	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Sheet rolling, aluminium	Lithium hexafluorophosphate	Nickel, 99.5%	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Tissue paper	Isopropyl acetate	Acetone liquid	Tap water	Tissue paper	Electricity, medium voltage				
Total	5.50E+01	1.42E-01	3.52E-01	1.07E-02	6.38E-03	1.63E+01	1.22E-01	1.46E+01	4.00E+00	1.30E-01	1.05E+01	7.81E+00	3.20E-02	2.66E-04	2.08E-03	1.16E-03	2.38E-06	2.66E-04	1.58E-04	4.25E-04	1.58E-04	4.25E-04	9.59E-03
AP	3.84E+00	7.28E-03	1.80E-02	7.62E-04	3.34E-05	8.91E-01	7.43E-03	6.96E-01	5.40E-01	1.51E-02	1.45E+00	1.18E-01	4.32E-03	6.26E-06	1.64E-04	7.93E-05	1.25E-08	6.26E-06	3.98E-06	1.96E-05	3.98E-06	1.96E-05	4.89E-04
CC	6.59E+00	3.78E-02	7.54E-02	2.58E-03	1.45E-04	3.10E-01	3.68E-02	1.71E+00	1.30E+00	4.57E-02	2.65E+00	1.61E-02	1.04E-02	2.25E-05	6.34E-04	3.61E-04	5.42E-08	2.25E-05	1.95E-05	1.28E-04	1.95E-05	1.28E-04	2.05E-03
FEx	5.18E-01	4.09E-03	4.67E-03	9.80E-05	5.76E-06	6.85E-02	4.08E-04	2.09E-01	3.34E-02	1.65E-03	1.69E-01	1.51E-03	2.67E-04	1.67E-06	3.83E-05	3.50E-06	2.15E-09	1.67E-06	6.37E-07	4.79E-07	6.37E-07	4.79E-07	1.27E-04
PM	3.47E+00	2.37E-02	3.08E-02	1.29E-03	1.90E-05	2.89E-01	1.06E-02	7.28E-01	9.28E-01	1.94E-02	1.37E+00	2.06E-02	7.43E-03	9.99E-06	2.04E-04	9.64E-05	7.10E-09	9.99E-06	1.60E-06	3.08E-05	1.60E-06	3.08E-05	8.37E-04
ME	4.85E-01	1.04E-03	3.21E-03	1.42E-04	5.65E-06	5.95E-02	1.62E-03	1.23E-01	7.74E-02	2.29E-03	2.02E-01	2.18E-03	6.19E-04	1.76E-06	2.60E-05	1.62E-05	2.11E-09	1.76E-06	6.74E-07	5.04E-06	6.74E-07	5.04E-06	8.73E-05
FE	1.48E+00	2.30E-05	1.18E-03	4.53E-05	6.86E-06	1.14E+00	2.17E-04	1.04E-01	2.46E-02	1.01E-03	1.33E-01	1.43E-02	1.97E-04	7.34E-07	9.64E-06	1.30E-05	2.56E-09	7.34E-07	9.76E-07	1.66E-06	9.76E-07	1.66E-06	3.22E-05
TE	6.84E-01	1.58E-03	4.97E-03	2.14E-04	8.46E-06	1.04E-01	2.46E-03	1.65E-01	1.18E-01	3.46E-03	2.64E-01	4.36E-03	9.48E-04	1.93E-06	3.96E-05	2.45E-05	3.16E-09	1.93E-06	1.00E-06	7.49E-06	1.00E-06	7.49E-06	1.35E-04
HCT	2.63E-01	2.93E-05	4.99E-04	3.09E-04	1.72E-06	1.06E-01	2.30E-04	7.25E-02	5.54E-02	7.24E-04	2.34E-02	7.15E-04	4.43E-04	7.95E-07	4.06E-06	1.64E-06	6.43E-10	7.95E-07	1.52E-07	3.92E-07	1.52E-07	3.92E-07	1.36E-05
HCNT	1.58E+00	3.11E-04	1.33E-03	3.95E-04	5.11E-06	1.09E+00	4.20E-04	2.24E-01	1.18E-01	1.76E-03	1.19E-01	3.52E-03	9.44E-04	3.10E-06	1.64E-05	3.10E-06	1.91E-09	3.10E-06	4.41E-07	8.04E-07	4.41E-07	8.04E-07	3.62E-05
IR	2.13E-01	2.47E-03	2.99E-03	2.85E-05	7.62E-06	7.30E-03	3.11E-04	1.01E-01	6.80E-03	8.57E-04	8.67E-02	5.65E-04	5.44E-05	4.76E-05	1.40E-05	1.89E-07	2.84E-09	4.76E-05	1.15E-06	1.10E-07	1.15E-06	1.10E-07	8.14E-05
LU	5.32E-02	1.07E-05	6.58E-04	1.47E-05	1.39E-06	1.12E-02	3.64E-04	1.46E-02	2.57E-03	2.07E-04	2.27E-02	1.01E-04	2.05E-05	2.70E-06	3.63E-06	1.51E-08	5.20E-10	2.70E-06	1.83E-07	5.60E-09	1.83E-07	5.60E-09	1.79E-05
OD	1.44E-02	6.76E-07	2.24E-05	7.36E-06	2.70E-07	5.86E-03	5.23E-06	1.58E-03	3.73E-04	1.92E-05	6.42E-03	2.17E-06	2.98E-06	2.48E-08	2.47E-07	4.61E-09	1.01E-10	2.48E-08	3.28E-08	1.59E-09	3.28E-08	1.59E-09	6.10E-07
POD	1.19E+00	3.64E-03	1.22E-02	4.92E-04	1.38E-05	1.68E-01	6.43E-03	2.72E-01	2.05E-01	7.13E-03	4.75E-01	1.23E-02	1.64E-03	3.87E-06	1.81E-04	6.05E-05	5.14E-09	3.87E-06	1.62E-06	2.10E-05	1.62E-06	2.10E-05	3.31E-04
RU-foss	4.42E+00	6.03E-02	9.98E-02	3.93E-03	1.22E-04	2.03E-01	4.88E-02	1.28E+00	5.26E-01	2.52E-02	1.93E+00	9.23E-03	4.21E-03	1.02E-04	6.20E-04	4.41E-04	4.56E-08	1.02E-04	1.71E-05	1.98E-04	1.71E-05	1.98E-04	2.72E-03
RU-mm	1.97E+01	3.14E-06	8.55E-02	4.67E-05	2.76E-06	1.18E+01	1.31E-04	6.98E+00	2.38E-03	2.90E-03	8.03E-01	5.51E-03	1.90E-05	7.02E-07	4.78E-06	3.05E-06	1.03E-09	7.02E-07	8.16E-08	1.09E-07	8.16E-08	1.09E-07	2.33E-03
WU	1.05E+01	-6.83E-05	1.13E-02	3.59E-04	6.00E-03	7.80E-02	5.50E-03	1.92E+00	6.40E-02	3.00E-03	8.12E-01	7.60E+00	5.12E-04	5.95E-05	1.23E-04	5.46E-05	2.24E-06	5.95E-05	1.09E-04	1.10E-05	1.09E-04	1.10E-05	3.09E-04

Table 26 - SimaPro evaluation LIB pouch cell results with mPt, Part 1

Damage Category (Unit: mPt)	Total	Coating and drying process	Cell Assembly						Electrolyte filling and cell final sealing				Degassing			
			Electricity, medium voltage	Nitrogen, liquid	Polypropylene, granulate	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Nitrogen, liquid	Polypropylene, granulate	Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage					
Total	5.50E+01	1.08E-02	9.10E-04	3.03E-05	2.02E-02	2.81E-02	2.02E-03	6.98E-02	1.01E-04	2.53E-05	1.21E-04	3.53E-02	6.07E-01	1.21E-02	1.87E-03	6.07E-03
AP	3.84E+00	4.99E-04	1.01E-04	3.35E-06	2.24E-03	3.11E-03	2.24E-04	7.72E-03	1.12E-05	2.79E-06	1.34E-05	3.90E-03	6.71E-02	1.34E-03	2.07E-04	6.71E-04
CC	6.59E+00	3.26E-03	3.64E-04	1.21E-05	8.10E-03	1.13E-02	8.10E-04	2.80E-02	4.05E-05	1.01E-05	4.86E-05	1.41E-02	2.43E-01	4.86E-03	7.50E-04	2.43E-03
FEx	5.18E-01	1.22E-05	2.03E-05	6.74E-07	4.50E-04	6.26E-04	4.50E-05	1.55E-03	2.25E-06	5.62E-07	2.70E-06	7.86E-04	1.35E-02	2.70E-04	4.17E-05	1.35E-04
PM	3.47E+00	7.84E-04	4.44E-05	1.48E-06	9.88E-04	1.37E-03	9.88E-05	3.41E-03	4.93E-06	1.23E-06	5.92E-06	1.72E-03	2.96E-02	5.92E-04	9.15E-05	2.96E-04
ME	4.85E-01	1.28E-04	9.88E-06	3.29E-07	2.20E-04	3.05E-04	2.20E-05	7.58E-04	1.10E-06	2.74E-07	1.32E-06	3.83E-04	6.59E-03	1.32E-04	2.03E-05	6.59E-05
FE	1.48E+00	4.24E-05	5.73E-05	1.91E-06	1.27E-03	1.77E-03	1.27E-04	4.39E-03	6.36E-06	1.59E-06	7.63E-06	2.22E-03	3.82E-02	7.63E-04	1.18E-04	3.82E-04
TE	6.84E-01	1.91E-04	1.43E-05	4.76E-07	3.18E-04	4.42E-04	3.18E-05	1.10E-03	1.59E-06	3.97E-07	1.91E-06	5.55E-04	9.55E-03	1.91E-04	2.95E-05	9.55E-05
HCT	2.63E-01	9.98E-06	2.38E-06	7.93E-08	5.30E-05	7.36E-05	5.30E-06	1.83E-04	2.65E-07	6.62E-08	3.18E-07	9.25E-05	1.59E-03	3.18E-05	4.91E-06	1.59E-05
HCNT	1.58E+00	2.05E-05	1.39E-05	4.63E-07	3.09E-04	4.30E-04	3.09E-05	1.07E-03	1.55E-06	3.86E-07	1.85E-06	5.40E-04	9.28E-03	1.85E-04	2.87E-05	9.28E-05
IR	2.13E-01	2.79E-06	3.16E-06	1.05E-07	7.02E-05	9.76E-05	7.02E-06	2.42E-04	3.51E-07	8.77E-08	4.21E-07	1.23E-04	2.11E-03	4.21E-05	6.50E-06	2.11E-05
LU	5.32E-02	1.43E-07	6.26E-07	2.08E-08	1.39E-05	1.93E-05	1.39E-06	4.80E-05	6.95E-08	1.74E-08	8.35E-08	2.43E-05	4.18E-04	8.35E-06	1.29E-06	4.18E-06
OD	1.44E-02	4.05E-08	1.66E-07	5.53E-09	3.69E-06	5.13E-06	3.69E-07	1.27E-05	1.84E-08	4.61E-09	2.21E-08	6.44E-06	1.11E-04	2.21E-06	3.42E-07	1.11E-06
POD	1.19E+00	5.34E-04	2.65E-05	8.81E-07	5.89E-04	8.18E-04	5.89E-05	2.03E-03	2.94E-06	7.35E-07	3.53E-06	1.03E-03	1.77E-02	3.53E-04	5.45E-05	1.77E-04
RU-foss	4.42E+00	5.05E-03	2.41E-04	8.03E-06	5.37E-03	7.46E-03	5.37E-04	1.85E-02	2.68E-05	6.70E-06	3.22E-05	9.37E-03	1.61E-01	3.22E-03	4.97E-04	1.61E-03
RU-mm	1.97E+01	2.79E-06	1.48E-06	4.94E-08	3.30E-05	4.58E-05	3.30E-06	1.14E-04	1.65E-07	4.12E-08	1.98E-07	5.76E-05	9.90E-04	1.98E-05	3.05E-06	9.90E-06
WU	1.05E+01	2.79E-04	9.20E-06	3.06E-07	2.04E-04	2.84E-04	2.04E-05	7.05E-04	1.02E-06	2.55E-07	1.23E-06	3.57E-04	6.13E-03	1.23E-04	1.89E-05	6.13E-05

Table 27 - SimaPro evaluation LIB pouch cell results with mPt, Part 2

Damage Category (Unit: mPt)	Total	Cells characterization		PPE		Waste				
		Electricity, medium voltage	Electricity, medium voltage	Synthetic rubber	Polypropylene granulate	Waste graphical paper	Wastewater	Wastewater	Wastewater	Waste graphical paper
Total	5.50E+01	1.87E-03	6.07E-03	4.25E-02	1.90E-04	3.97E-02	-1.56E-03	-1.57E-03	-1.99E-03	3.97E-02
AP	3.84E+00	2.07E-04	6.71E-04	4.70E-03	2.10E-05	6.69E-04	1.14E-05	1.14E-05	1.44E-05	6.69E-04
CC	6.59E+00	7.50E-04	2.43E-03	1.70E-02	7.61E-05	3.10E-02	5.63E-05	5.65E-05	7.16E-05	3.10E-02

FEx	5.18E-01	4.17E-05	1.35E-04	9.46E-04	4.23E-06	2.66E-03	2.16E-04	2.17E-04	2.74E-04	2.66E-03
PM	3.47E+00	9.15E-05	2.96E-04	2.08E-03	9.28E-06	7.52E-04	1.21E-05	1.22E-05	1.54E-05	7.52E-04
ME	4.85E-01	2.03E-05	6.59E-05	4.62E-04	2.06E-06	1.16E-03	1.76E-04	1.77E-04	2.24E-04	1.16E-03
FE	1.48E+00	1.18E-04	3.82E-04	2.68E-03	1.20E-05	2.81E-05	1.98E-04	1.99E-04	2.52E-04	2.81E-05
TE	6.84E-01	2.95E-05	9.55E-05	6.69E-04	2.99E-06	5.52E-04	7.05E-06	7.09E-06	8.97E-06	5.52E-04
HCT	2.63E-01	4.91E-06	1.59E-05	1.11E-04	4.98E-07	2.07E-04	2.86E-06	2.87E-06	3.64E-06	2.07E-04
HCNT	1.58E+00	2.87E-05	9.28E-05	6.50E-04	2.91E-06	1.14E-03	6.11E-05	6.14E-05	7.78E-05	1.14E-03
IR	2.13E-01	6.50E-06	2.11E-05	1.48E-04	6.60E-07	2.48E-06	1.69E-06	1.70E-06	2.15E-06	2.48E-06
LU	5.32E-02	1.29E-06	4.18E-06	2.93E-05	1.31E-07	4.86E-05	6.04E-07	6.07E-07	7.68E-07	4.86E-05
OD	1.44E-02	3.42E-07	1.11E-06	7.75E-06	3.47E-08	1.08E-06	2.36E-08	2.37E-08	3.00E-08	1.08E-06
POD	1.19E+00	5.45E-05	1.77E-04	1.24E-03	5.53E-06	1.32E-03	7.10E-06	7.13E-06	9.03E-06	1.32E-03
RU-foss	4.42E+00	4.97E-04	1.61E-03	1.13E-02	5.04E-05	7.47E-04	2.91E-05	2.92E-05	3.70E-05	7.47E-04
RU-mm	1.97E+01	3.05E-06	9.90E-06	6.93E-05	3.10E-07	1.92E-05	5.41E-06	5.44E-06	6.88E-06	1.92E-05
WU	1.05E+01	1.89E-05	6.13E-05	4.30E-04	1.92E-06	-5.34E-04	-2.35E-03	-2.36E-03	-2.99E-03	-5.34E-04

Table 28 - SimaPro evaluation LIB pouch cell results with mPt, Part 3

